

Project Title: 'Trauma and dementia diagnosis: An investigation of the potential for a trauma-informed pathway through the diagnosis of dementia, for people under 65 years old'.

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For Rory and my dad.

Abbreviation List

Adverse childhood experiences – ACE

Alzheimer's disease – AD

Alzheimer Scotland – AS

Alzheimer Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice – ASCPP

Critical Appraisal Skills Programme – CASP

Dementia Engagement and Empowerment Project – DEEP

Frontotemporal dementia – FTD

Magnetic resonance imaging – MRI

National Dementia Carers Action Network – NDCAN

National Health Service – NHS

NHS Education for Scotland – NES

NHS Integrated Research Application System – IRAS

Post-diagnostic support – PDS

Post-traumatic growth – PTG

Qualitative descriptive research – QDR

Scottish Dementia Research Consortium – SDRC

Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration – SAMHSA

Trauma-informed care – TIC

Trauma-informed principles – TIP

United Kingdom – UK

University of the West of Scotland – UWS

Vascular dementia – VD

Young-onset dementia – YOD

Abstract

Young Onset Dementia (YOD) refers to dementia diagnosed in people under the age of 65. Unlike dementia in older adults, YOD often affects people who are still working, raising families, and managing active relationships. Receiving a diagnosis can be a long and stressful process, which increases the risk of psychological distress and trauma for both individuals and their families.

Currently, there is limited understanding of how trauma-informed care, an approach that recognises and responds to the impact of trauma, can be used to support people with YOD and their carers throughout the diagnostic journey. Health professionals may find it difficult to identify trauma or its effects, which can lead to unmet needs before and after diagnosis.

This study aimed to explore the experiences of individuals with YOD, their families, and the healthcare professionals involved in their diagnosis. Using interviews with nine participants (three people with YOD, three carers/family members, and three health professionals), the five trauma-informed principles: safety, choice, trustworthiness, collaboration and empowerment were used to explore how they could improve the diagnostic pathway.

Participants were recruited through established networks, and interviews were conducted in Lanarkshire between September 2024 and February 2025. Data were analysed to identify how trauma-informed principles could be integrated into practice.

Findings showed that if a sense of safety is not established before diagnosis, it becomes difficult to meet the other trauma-informed principles later. This can undermine support after diagnosis and leave ongoing needs unmet.

This research highlights the importance of embedding trauma-informed care early in the YOD diagnostic process. By doing so, health professionals can better support individuals and families, reduce distress, and improve overall experiences throughout the dementia journey.

Key Words

Young-onset dementia ~ dementia ~ trauma ~ trauma-informed principles ~ trauma-informed approach ~ trauma-informed practices ~ diagnostic pathway

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We the undersigned agree to the terms, as detailed above, related to the authorship and acknowledgment.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Content

This section provides a comprehensive definition of young-onset dementia (YOD) and explores the integration of trauma-informed principles within its diagnostic pathway. Trauma-informed principles are foundational guidelines used in health, education, social care, and other service sectors to support individuals who have experienced trauma. These principles recognise the widespread impact of trauma and aim to create environments that promote healing, safety, and empowerment. By examining how these principles can influence and improve the diagnostic process, the section also highlights the broader implications of adopting this approach. Together, these insights establish the essential background and underpinning rationale for this study.

1.2 Young Onset Dementia

When a person develops symptoms of dementia under the age of 65 years, it is referred to as 'young-onset dementia' (YOD) (Dementia UK, 2023). Potentially, 3.9 million individuals worldwide between the ages of 30 and 64 live with YOD (Hendriks et al., 2022), and approximately 70,800 people in the United Kingdom (UK) are currently living with YOD (Alzheimer's Society, 2021). YOD is most commonly the result of Alzheimer's disease (AD), with an estimated 1 in 3 people with YOD being affected (Alzheimer's Research UK, 2023). AD is thought to be the result of a malfunction in the brain involving two proteins called amyloid (plaques) and tau (tangles) (Breijyeh and Karaman, 2020; Dementia UK, 2022). The risk of dementia could be reduced by improving 14 modifiable risk factors, including smoking, depression, physical inactivity and excessive alcohol consumption (Livingston et al., 2024). Experiencing traumatic life events can lead to an increased risk of developing dementia due to changes in the brain (Severs et al., 2023).

The term 'dementia' is predominantly associated with older adults and the diagnostic pathway and support available for those with YOD can often feel disjointed; therefore, specialised, appropriate support is crucial (Tolhurst, Bhattacharyya and Kingston, 2012; Ritchie et al., 2015). Adults over 65 years old with AD often present with memory loss, agitation, growing anxiety and apathy (Simonetti et al., 2020), whereas the presentation of YOD is often 'atypical' (O'Malley et al., 2021). Progressive language difficulties, including the ability to speak fluently, verbal expression, behavioural and

psychological changes, and corticobasal syndrome (motor dysfunction), are reported (Banovic, Zunic, and Sinanovic, 2018; Graff-Radford et al., 2021). Frontotemporal dementia (FTD) is also common in younger people and is the second most common type of dementia affecting those under 65 years old (Young et al., 2017; Chiari et al., 2020). FTD represents the degradation of cells in the frontal and anterior temporal lobes (Kurz et al., 2014). The frontal and temporal cortices are associated with behavioural changes, progressive aphasia, and semantic knowledge, which is connecting meanings to words and applying them in the correct context (Bang, Spina and Miller, 2015; Lupyan and Lewis, 2017). The behavioural variant of FTD can be mistaken for a mental health issue. This is evident in obsessive-compulsive behaviours, resulting in misdiagnosis, particularly with someone younger, resulting in an extended period on the diagnostic pathway (Draper et al., 2016). Woollacott and Rohrer (2016) suggest that people under 65 presenting with atypical symptoms of FTD should receive a cognitive examination. This should explore family history and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) to enhance clinician understanding of visual changes in the brain associated with FTD. This could enable early detection and the quicker implementation of appropriate support throughout the diagnostic process.

According to Mayrhofer et al. (2017), there is a lack of consistent services for those living with YOD, and support is often short-term or ad hoc. Rodda and Carter., (2016) highlighted that individuals with YOD were disappointed in the lack of appropriate services regarding diagnostic support, social support activities, and care facilities. A lack of age-appropriate support and care, coupled with the social and interpersonal impact of a diagnosis, such as loss of identity and isolation (Carter, 2022) could lead to an individual questioning their role and goals in life, causing identity stress, which can be linked to developing trauma (Berman, Montgomery and Ratner, 2020). Receiving a YOD diagnosis can ultimately lead to emotional stress (Brough, Drummond and Biggs, 2018). Bannon et al., (2022) suggested that YOD post-diagnosis stressors can encompass various themes: impact of diagnosis, social and family relationships, changing roles and responsibilities, planning for an uncertain future and couple communication and relationship strain, emphasising successful collaboration and meaningful communication to promote positive interactions throughout these themes. Feelings of uncertainty about the future in the diagnostic pathway are a burden for families (Hall and Sikes, 2018), which can start pre-diagnosis

due to diagnostic delays (García-Toro et al., 2018). The dementia diagnostic needs of those under 65 years old are complex and attention to the heightened risk of psychological stress must be recognised in support services (Wiggins, McEwen and Sexton, 2022). Adapting to the needs of those with YOD and their families is crucial in managing emotional distress and supporting people to live well with dementia (O'Malley et al., 2019).

Past trauma can increase the risk of developing anxiety disorders, where improved support services rooted in trauma-informed approaches can prevent re-traumatisation (Hogg et al., 2022). A dementia diagnosis may heighten the emotional response to potential triggers in individuals who have experienced (Bruneau, Desmarais and Pokrzywko, 2020).

1.3 Trauma and Trauma-Informed Principles

Trauma can result from a single event or a series of events where an individual experiences physical or mental harm. Type 1 trauma is defined as a one-off event, with type 2 trauma relating to a series of events over a prolonged period (Copeland et al., 2018). Both types can have a lasting detrimental effect, impacting an individual's cognitive, physical, social, or emotional well-being (Blehm, 2024). Traumatic experiences in early life called Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACEs), such as volatile home life, abuse, neglect or bereavement, can influence well-being in adulthood (Brodie et al., 2023). Emotional trauma can happen at any time from childhood to adulthood, which can lead to negative thoughts and behaviours at any stage in life (Giotakos, 2020; Brown, Baker and Wilcox, 2012).

Traumatic experiences can introduce new stressors and potentially re-traumatise individuals due to triggers of historical life events (Pazderka et al., 2021). It is estimated that 70%-90% of individuals who engage with mental health services have experienced trauma in their lives (Neill and Read, 2022). Healthcare staff should understand how past trauma can affect individuals and their families when delivering person-centred care (Hennessy, Hunter, and Grealish, 2022).

Trauma-informed care (TIC) is an approach utilised by health practitioners to recognise trauma prevalence and apply practices to reduce the risk of re-traumatising

individuals (Yatchmenoff, Sundborg and Davis, 2017). TIC is rooted in providing a safe environment (Collin-Vézina, Brend and Beeman, 2020) and promoting empowerment through healthy coping mechanisms (Ardley, Goodloe and Kerns, 2020). Re-traumatisation can present in various ways, including distress, physical illness, and concentration difficulties (Goddard, 2021), which necessitate knowledge from health practitioners to identify and assess (Barrett, 2019). Building a trusting relationship between healthcare providers and service users will foster feelings of safety, empowerment, and resilience, all key aspects of TIC (Barrett, 2019).

Understanding of the long-lasting impact of trauma can help healthcare practitioners recognise the signs of trauma and potential traumatisation (SAMHSA, 2024). SAMHSA (2024) utilises these principles in its mental health services to establish a recovery-focused system.

Figure 1. Trauma Informed Systems

This image from the Trauma-Informed Practice: A Toolkit for Scotland visually represents the complex layers of trauma-informed systems and foundational components of trauma-informed practice. Each layer represents a conceptual domain:

- **Outer Layer:** This layer emphasises contextual and relational dimensions, featuring the phrases "*TRAUMA-INFORMED,*" "*CULTURAL AND HISTORICAL CONTEXT,*" and "*RELATIONSHIPS MATTER.*" These elements underscore the importance of situating trauma-informed approaches within broader socio-cultural frameworks and prioritizing interpersonal connections.
- **Middle Layer:** This section outlines four key operational principles: "*REALISE PREVALENCE,*" "*RECOGNISE IMPACT,*" "*RESPOND,*" and "*RESIST RETRAUMATISATION.*" These guide the implementation of trauma-informed strategies across systems and services.
- **Inner Layer:** At this level, the diagram highlights core values and systemic considerations, including "*RESPECT RESILIENCE,*" and "*GENDER POLICIES, SYSTEMS, ENVIRONMENTS AND PEOPLE.*" These reflect the commitment to equity, empowerment, and structural sensitivity.
- **Central Core:** The heart of the diagram consists of five overlapping-coloured shapes, each labelled with a central principle of trauma-informed practice:
 - **Green:** *Choice*
 - **Blue:** *Collaboration*
 - **Purple:** *Empowerment*
 - **Red:** *Trust*
 - **Teal:** *Safety*

Figure 2. Impact of trauma and adversity in the absence of buffers/protective factors

This image, titled "Impact of trauma and adversity in the absence of buffers/protective factors", is sourced from *Trauma-Informed Practice: A Toolkit for Scotland* (Homes and Grandison, 2021, p. 69) uses the metaphor of a tree to illustrate the cumulative and systemic effects of trauma across the lifespan.

- **Roots:** The base of the tree represents the origins of trauma, categorised into four types:
 - *Childhood Single Incident Trauma*
 - *Childhood Complex Trauma*
 - *Adult Single Incident Trauma*
 - *Adult Complex Trauma*

These roots signify the foundational experiences that contribute to long-term adversity.

- **Trunk and Lower Labels:** The central part of the tree includes labels such as *“Difficulty managing strong emotions,” “Risky strategies to manage distress,”* and *“Difficulties with relationships with others i.e. trust,”* indicating the internal and interpersonal challenges that often emerge from unresolved trauma.
- **Branches:** The upper part of the tree illustrates the broader societal and health-related consequences of trauma, including:
 - Higher rates of preventable disease
 - Higher risk of early death
 - Educational difficulties
 - Relationship risks
 - Reduced opportunities
 - Contact with the justice system
 - Higher rates of substance misuse and other health-harming behaviours
 - Higher risk of all mental health difficulties
 - Higher risk of further harm

These outcomes reflect the pervasive impact of trauma when protective factors are absent, emphasising the need for trauma-informed systems and interventions.

Trauma-informed approaches involve applying the key principles in practice: 1. Safety, 2. trustworthiness, 3. Choice, 4. Collaboration, 5. Empowerment (Scottish Government, 2021). Using the five principles, NHS Education for Scotland (NES) developed a range of learning tools to support services in building trauma-informed practice and knowledge in the workplace (NHS Education for Scotland, 2024). To foster a trauma-informed workforce NES encourage the use of the 5 R’s:

- Realising how common the experience of trauma and adversity is
- Recognising the different ways that trauma can affect people

- Responding by taking account of the ways that people can be affected by trauma to support recovery, and recognise and support Resilience
- Opportunities to Resist re-traumatisation and offer a greater sense of choice and control, empowerment, collaboration and safety with everyone that you have contact with
- Recognising the central importance of Relationships

Incorporating trauma-informed principles (TIP) in person-centred care enables practitioners to consider all environments, past and present, and how traumatic memories may influence long-term perceptions (Kusmaul and Anderson, 2018). Individuals respond to life events differently, and what may be traumatic for some people can elicit a positive response with resilience in others (Kusmaul and Anderson, 2018). A trauma-informed practitioner can create an environment promoting TIP, which could enhance knowledge of recognising emotional vulnerability and avoiding re-traumatisation (Levenson, 2017).

1.3.1 Safety

Creating an emotionally and physically safe environment in support services requires health professionals to be transparent in their communication, provide flexible, person-centred care, and ensure a balance of power in decision-making (Isobel et al., 2020). Not only is it important to establish safety initially, but it must also be ongoing throughout support, with continuous risk assessment and awareness of potential triggers to feeling unsafe (Aven, 2022). When feeling unsafe, individuals experience uncertainty in everyday life, leading to anxiety and emotional stress (Morriss et al., 2022). TIC is rooted in promoting safety and eliminating feelings of threat or tension in the delivery of care (Lackner, 2024).

1.3.2 Trustworthiness

According to Ahmed, (2023), building a trusting relationship requires regular, meaningful engagement to understand perspectives and to gain a positive rapport. Individuals are more likely to feel trust when they believe they can express their feelings freely without judgment, which leads to positive outcomes (Anderson and Griffith, 2022). Both Bührmann et al. (2022) and Metz et al. (2021) share several key features when defining trustworthiness, as they emphasise the importance of

displaying empathy through authentic collaboration in fostering trusting relationships. Implementing open communication between healthcare providers and service users can foster trusting relationships (Metz et al., 2022).

1.3.3 Choice

Those living with a dementia diagnosis must have independence, choice, and autonomy over decisions in their care (Bhatt et al., 2018), a principle supported by health professionals who promote autonomy and psychological well-being (van Oppen et al., 2022). Individuals with a cognitive impairment should be well-informed and given clear information on the choices they have in their care to fully engage with their own decision-making (Florijn et al., 2024).

1.3.4 Collaboration

Successful collaboration is a result of mutual trust, the sharing of knowledge, and continuity (Rosenlund et al., 2024), which fosters positive engagement among healthcare providers and service users (Ekman, Ebrahimi, and Olaya Contreras, 2021). A trusting relationship between support services and service users is often viewed as a prerequisite for successful collaboration (Hoek et al., 2020). Interprofessional collaboration, moving beyond referral processes, is equally important to share best practices and enhance patient experiences (Seaton et al., 2020).

1.3.5 Empowerment

For those living with dementia, empowerment through choice, identity and purpose can support adaptability in processing their diagnosis and enhance their capabilities (van Corven et al., 2022). When offered the opportunity to engage in meaningful activities which enhance their self-worth and fulfil their social contribution to their community, they can experience empowerment throughout their dementia diagnosis (Berit Ziebuhr et al., 2023).

1.4 Young Onset Dementia and Trauma-Informed Approach

A dementia diagnosis, given its profound impact, places individuals and their families at risk of trauma throughout the diagnostic pathway (Scottish Government, 2023). The

diagnostic process itself can introduce psychological risk (Sansoni et al., 2016), particularly in YOD, where accelerated cognitive decline and diagnostic delays (Loi et al., 2020; Kvello-Alme et al., 2021) often impede timely treatment, support, and care planning, intensifying distress for both individuals and families (Prince, Bryce & Ferri, 2011; Rasmussen & Langerman, 2019). Despite these risks, the criteria for a 'quality' diagnostic experience remain unclear, and whether trauma considerations are adequately integrated into this process is yet to be explored (Pickett et al., 2018).

Individuals with YOD may have additional psychosocial stressors due to their age, such as having to leave their employment (Rabanal et al., 2018). Being diagnosed with dementia in an active stage of life can intensify emotional stress as families navigate a progressive illness with limited support services suited to their needs (Grunberg et al., 2021). Stamou et al., (2021) indicates providing consistency through these support services of YOD in both pre-diagnosis and post-diagnosis can reduce the emotional stress.

The literature lacks comprehensive coverage of a trauma-informed approach within dementia and the sub-types such as YOD, however there is emerging research in this field where the wider recognition of the TI paradigm is highlighted. Craftsman et al. (2019) suggest that applying a trauma-informed lens to a dementia diagnosis may reduce the risk of trauma and re-traumatisation. This approach may benefit individuals with YOD, as they may experience prolonged and heightened stress due to diagnostic delays which could potentially lead to trauma or re-traumatisation (Loi et al., 2020; Chiari et al., 2022). The integration of accurate and timely diagnosis into person-centred care can enhance the long-term engagement of individuals living with YOD (Loi, Cations, and Velakoulis, 2023).

Trauma, and reactivation of trauma may be difficult for health care professionals to recognise (Magruder, McLaughlin and Elmore Borbon, 2017) and a trauma-informed framework dedicated to the YOD pathway may improve communication between patients and their families, as well as clinician awareness and support.

1.5 Summary

The literature highlights the complex and multifactorial nature of Young Onset Dementia (YOD), with atypical presentations and diagnostic challenges that often delay appropriate support. These delays, coupled with the emotional and social consequences of a diagnosis, can contribute to psychological distress and trauma for both individuals and their families. The evidence suggests that trauma, whether historical or emerging from the diagnostic experience, can exacerbate cognitive and emotional vulnerabilities, particularly in younger individuals. Integrating trauma-informed principles into dementia care is therefore essential. This approach promotes safety, trust, empowerment, and collaboration, helping to mitigate the risk of re-traumatisation and support emotional resilience. By recognising the intersection between trauma and dementia, especially in YOD, services can be better tailored to meet the nuanced needs of this population, aligning with project aims to enhance diagnostic pathways, improve service responsiveness, and foster compassionate, person-centred care.

This project aims to understand the diagnostic experience of people with young onset dementia and their families, investigating how a trauma-informed framework can potentially improve their diagnostic experience.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

This chapter presents a scoping review of the existing literature on trauma-informed approaches to the diagnostic pathway for young-onset dementia (YOD). The review aims to explore how principles of trauma-informed practice (TIP) have been considered in the diagnostic experiences of individuals under 65 diagnosed with dementia. Specifically, the review investigates whether key features of TIP (e.g., safety, trustworthiness, peer support, collaboration, empowerment, and cultural sensitivity) have been addressed in studies on YOD diagnosis, and whether trauma-related experiences are reflected in the literature.

The review followed the methodological framework proposed by Arksey and O'Malley (2005), which is appropriate for mapping broad and complex areas of research. This review is best described as a scoping review, as it does not include the iterative, interpretive engagement typical of reflexive thematic analysis. The process involved identifying relevant studies through systematic searches of peer-reviewed and grey literature, applying a diagnosis of dementia focused on age (under 65), diagnostic experiences, and trauma-informed concepts.

Despite the growing interest in trauma-informed care, the synthesis of findings revealed limited direct application of TIP principles to the YOD diagnostic pathway. However, several studies indirectly referenced trauma-related experiences, such as emotional distress, identity disruption, and systemic barriers during diagnosis. These findings suggest a gap in the literature where trauma-informed frameworks could be more explicitly applied to improve diagnostic experiences for people with YOD.

2.2 Literature review method

The framework outlined by Arksey and O'Malley (2005) provided the method for the scoping review –

Stage 1: identifying the research question.

Stage 2: identifying relevant studies

Stage 3: study selection

Stage 4: charting the data

Stage 5: collating, summarizing and reporting the results

2.3 Searching and sourcing

The literature search strategy included online databases, including PubMed (NCBI), MEDLINE, CINAHL, and Google Scholar. These databases are recognised as reliable sources for supporting healthcare research and identifying knowledge gaps (Oermann et al., 2021). The search terms included words directly related to the research. The researcher reviewed abstracts from the search. Further screening of

the full text concluded whether the paper was eligible. The Boolean operator 'AND' was used to pair relevant words and terms.

The researcher met with a University of the West of Scotland (UWS) librarian who utilised their expertise in literature searches and demonstrated various techniques to maximise research results.

There were no specific inclusion or exclusion criteria in the search strategy. The search spanned the years from 2010 to 2024. All papers were in English.

Search terms - Young-onset dementia ~ dementia ~ trauma ~ trauma-informed principles ~ trauma-informed approach ~ trauma-informed practices ~ diagnostic pathway

2.4 Quality appraisal

To ensure the rigour and relevance of the studies included in this literature review, the **Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP)** checklist for qualitative research was employed and can be seen in Appendix 1. The CASP tool is widely recognised for its clarity and accessibility, particularly for early career researchers working in healthcare and social research contexts (Long, French, & Brooks, 2020). It provides a structured framework for evaluating the trustworthiness, relevance, and results of the studies in this literature review.

The CASP checklist consists of ten key questions that assess aspects such as:

- The clarity of the research aims
- The appropriateness of the methodology
- The research design and recruitment strategy
- Data collection and ethical considerations
- The rigour of data analysis
- The clarity of findings
- The value of the research

Each study was reviewed against these criteria, and responses were recorded in an Excel spreadsheet (see Appendix 2 for an example). This spreadsheet included

columns for each CASP question, allowing the researcher to note whether each criterion was met, partially met, or not met, along with brief justifications or observations. This process helped to systematically assess the quality of each study and ensure transparency in the selection process.

The appraisal process also supported the identification of studies that were methodologically sound and thematically relevant to the review's focus on trauma-informed practice (TIP) and the diagnostic pathway of young-onset dementia (YOD). Studies that scored poorly on key CASP criteria such as lacking ethical clarity or insufficient data analysis were excluded or flagged for cautious interpretation.

Following the appraisal, thematic grouping was used to organise the findings. This involved identifying recurring themes across the studies, such as:

- Emotional and psychological impact of diagnosis
- Experiences of healthcare professionals
- Barriers to trauma-informed care
- Coping mechanisms and support systems

This thematic approach enabled the researcher to synthesise insights across diverse studies and highlight gaps in the literature, particularly around the integration of trauma-informed principles in diagnostic services for people under 65 with dementia (McAllister et al., 2020).

In total, 13 studies were included in the final review. These studies varied in geographical context, methodological approach, and focus, but collectively contributed to a deeper understanding of how trauma-informed care can shape the diagnostic experience for individuals with YOD. The 13 studies are outlined in Appendix 3.

2.5 Literature Review Findings

The studies included in the literature review examined the pathway of a YOD diagnosis and were all qualitative. This included daily living, diagnostic aspects, trauma-informed approaches and life-altering illnesses. There was no evidence of literature relating directly to applying TIP principles to the YOD diagnostic pathway.

Originally, exploring papers from 2015-2024, due to a lack of literature, the year search was expanded from 2010-2024.

Those receiving a diagnosis of YOD and their family/carers are experiencing emotional distress throughout the diagnostic pathway, which was highlighted recently by the Scottish Government, (2023). This stress may lead to trauma or re-traumatisation, which could be improved by adopting a trauma-informed pathway. A diagnosis of YOD can ultimately lead to a sense of identity loss and a lack of empowerment. The studies highlighted the importance of collaboration among individuals with YOD, their families and carers, and health professionals. Health professionals can potentially make a more meaningful impact with enhanced knowledge of how to recognise trauma and re-traumatisation in an individual's YOD diagnostic journey (Lai et al, 2022) The literature was divided into four themes: 'Coping with the Daily Stresses of YOD' 'Diagnostic Pathway of YOD', 'Trauma-Informed Approach', and 'Life-altering Diagnosis'. The following section examines the literature by first considering how daily life, both before and after diagnosis, influences this journey, as it runs parallel to the diagnostic pathway.

2.6.1 Coping with the daily stresses of a YOD diagnosis

Gerritsen et al. (2018) conducted a 2-year longitudinal study in the Netherlands, involving 198 male and female participants with a mean age of 60.9 years. The study investigated the decline of cognitive function in individuals diagnosed with YOD. It characterised three subtypes of YOD, which were Alzheimer's dementia (AD), vascular dementia (VD) and frontotemporal dementia (FTD). The study found a significant progression of dementia severity over the two years, with AD subtype participants showing the most significant decline; however, no relationship to why this happened was found. Using CASP, the study was found to have a clearly focused issue and appropriate methodology, but limitations were noted in its ability to account for confounding factors, particularly regarding the lack of explanation for the differential

progression rates. A follow-up study by Gerritsen et al., (2019), 38.9% of the participants from the initial study died. These findings present an alarming rate of YOD-related mortality, suggesting the importance of understanding the diagnostic pathway for YOD, which is currently overlooked, and the lack of understanding of how to support a person with YOD to live well with appropriate support and truly understand lived experiences (O'Malley et al., 2019). However, Gerritsen et al. (2019) did not have access to death certificates where the information was given from relatives; therefore, an accurate account of the cause of death and comorbidity cannot be specified, suggesting various other factors contributed to death. Notably, the studies by Gerritsen et al., (2018, 2019) highlight the rapid decline in those with YOD, suggesting the knowledge gap when addressing the unmet needs of those with a diagnosis of YOD potentially due to a prolonged diagnostic pathway, and limited access to support services (Baptista et al., 2016).

Throughout their lifetime, most of the general population reports having experienced a potentially traumatic event or experience at least once (Knipscheer et al., 2020). Studies like Dunham et al. (2019) highlight that a diagnosis of dementia may present trauma or re-traumatisation, which aligns with the recent recognition from the Scottish Government (2021). However, there is a lack of literature addressing whether TIC is being applied and delivered through age-appropriate YOD services across the UK (Rodda and Carter, 2015). Building on previous research will be critical, like the study by Rabanal et al., (2018), which considered 14 people who already have a diagnosis of YOD living in the UK. Using interpretative phenomenological analysis, key issues identified included the difficulties in obtaining a conclusive diagnosis and the lack of consistent face-to-face support. Participants highlighted that YOD is underrepresented in the knowledge of health professionals, thus causing delays in accessing support networks. Comprehending the influence of age in YOD diagnosis on emotional distress is of critical importance. The study highlighted that eight of the participants were currently active in the UK workforce when they received a diagnosis of YOD, and each participant retired. One participant reported it was 'devastating' to retire early, presenting them with various psychosocial barriers which had a detrimental effect on coming to terms with their diagnosis. This impacted their day-to-day lives and significantly disrupted their life trajectory.

Johannessen et al. (2018) conducted a qualitative longitudinal study in Norway involving individuals (n=10) living alone with a diagnosis of YOD. The study focused on the participants' daily experiences and coping strategies throughout their illness. The study demonstrates the importance of recognising existential anxiety post-diagnosis when faced with day-to-day activities and reported having 'serious morning anxiety' and often panicking if the doorbell rings. Additionally, one participant indicated that this feeling stems from an overwhelming sense of losing control and identity due to their YOD diagnosis, which in turn affects their regular activities. These results support that there is a direct link between a diagnosis of YOD and an increased risk of mental health conditions (Radvile Medeisyte et al., 2025). The study was critically appraised using the CASP tool, which confirmed its methodological rigour and relevance. It met key criteria including a clear statement of aims, appropriate qualitative methodology, and ethical considerations. However, limitations were noted in the transparency of the recruitment strategy and reflexivity of the researchers. Despite this, the study produced rich, quality data reflecting the honest and unique experiences of daily living after a dementia diagnosis. The findings can support the development of appropriate post-diagnostic support services, integrating care for both YOD and broader mental health issues (Bamford et al., 2021).

A study by Clemerson, Walsh and Isaac, (2013) interviewed individuals with a diagnosis of YOD, exploring the perspective of someone younger living with dementia and how they cope with everyday life. Eight participants were recruited through NHS services in Britain with a diagnosis of YOD. Participants were community-dwelling in their own homes, not in employment, with an age range of 35 to 65 years old. Using interpretative phenomenological analysis, four superordinate themes emerged: disruption of the life cycle, identity, social orientation, and agency. The interruption in the life cycle and social identity had a significantly negative impact post-diagnosis in the study, which can be linked to developing trauma (Berman, Montgomery and Ratner, 2020). Although the evidence on trauma and sense of identity is still in its infancy, drawing on the work of Berman, Montgomery and Ratner, (2020) that highlighted the intersection between trauma and identity in adolescents, it may be the case that the disruption in identity experienced post-diagnosis is a proximal risk factor linked with trauma in this population. Further work on this complex relationship was not identified in this literature review. While it may represent a gap in the evidence

base, it does relate to the everyday challenges of a diagnosis and how this may contribute to vulnerability to trauma. When confronted with a traumatic event, an individual may feel a sense of inner strength when reflecting on their existential awareness (Malhotra and Suma Chebiyan, 2016). The study was critically appraised using the CASP Qualitative Checklist, which confirmed its relevance and methodological appropriateness. It clearly stated its aims and used a suitable qualitative approach (IPA) to explore lived experiences. Ethical considerations were addressed, and the data collection methods were appropriate for the research question. However, the study lacked detailed discussion on researcher reflexivity and potential bias, which may influence interpretation. Despite this, the findings were well-supported by participant quotations, enhancing credibility. Participants spoke of the shock they experienced after diagnosis with an overwhelming feeling that they were 'too young' to have dementia. Participants were often not ready to leave their place of employment but were 'forced' to take early retirement. The study suggested that limiting specific roles can lead to identity challenges. Participants who developed coping strategies, such as accepting themselves, connecting with others, and learning about their diagnosis, experienced positive outcomes. Pallesen (2013) suggested that support from healthcare professionals in addressing the challenges identified in Clemerson, Walsh, and Isaac's (2013) study can significantly enhance self-perception.

2.6.2 Diagnostic Pathway of YOD

Exploring both pre- and post-diagnosis of YOD, Loi et al. (2022) conducted interviews with 242 individuals who had been diagnosed with YOD. Clear themes were established by the researchers, highlighting a long and painful process when navigating their dementia diagnosis journey. The findings of a lengthy and complex journey from symptom onset to diagnosis are substantiated by several studies in this review (Draper et al., 2016; O'Malley et al., 2021; Novek et al., 2016). Loi et al. (2022) emphasise the importance of information sharing and guidance from the pre-diagnosis stage onward. Additionally, the prolonged uncertainty of receiving a diagnosis and the complexity of emotions thereafter significantly increase anxiety experienced by both those with the diagnosis and the family/carers. The study focused on participants who all reported they felt well-supported by a strong family network but still felt high levels of anxiety. This is concerning as persistent feelings of loneliness throughout a YOD diagnosis may cause further distress (Sundström et al., 2019). The study also

emphasises the importance of YOD awareness among health professionals as they are key in sharing information with families to support them in making informed decisions. The research question was clearly focused, and the qualitative design was appropriate for exploring lived experiences across a large sample. Data collection methods were robust, and ethical considerations were addressed. However, the study's large sample size for a qualitative design raises questions about depth versus breadth of analysis, and the paper provided limited detail on how researcher bias and reflexivity were managed. Despite these limitations, the findings were clearly presented and supported by participant narratives, enhancing credibility and transferability.

Busted, Nielsen, and Birkelund (2020) focused on the experience of YOD post-diagnosis, conducting a qualitative study with a total of nine participants (five male and four female) who had been diagnosed with YOD. A central theme emerging was the overwhelming feelings of loss of identity and fear of the future experienced by those throughout their diagnosis of YOD. The findings highlighted those with YOD as having a 'painful loss of sense of self'. This resulted from feelings of humiliation about the future, becoming a burden to friends and family, and losing control of their lives. Given the prolonged length of a YOD diagnostic pathway alongside the progressive nature of YOD symptoms, age-appropriate support must start pre-diagnosis at symptom onset (Lai et al., 2022)

For those under 65 years old diagnosed with dementia, this loss is viewed as a disruption of nature's life cycle (Clemerson, Walsh and Isaac, 2013). There is a lack of research exploring how to support the unique challenges faced by those with YOD in the diagnostic pathway and future (Loi et al., 2022). A historical or new traumatic event can trigger the development of identity loss (Waterman, 2020), creating a complex relationship between facing a dementia diagnosis and previous traumatic experiences (Desmarais et al., 2020).

Busted, Nielsen, and Birkelund., (2020) found that the participants with YOD clearly stated they wanted to have their voice heard in their diagnosis journey and favoured the use of advanced technology, such as location trackers, to navigate daily life safely after a YOD diagnosis. When considering someone being diagnosed with dementia before the age of 65, meaningful approaches would create a sense of purpose and

routine, for example, relevant workplace interventions (Richardson et al., 2016). This aligns with Busted, Nielsen, and Birkelund., (2020) proposal for the continued need for a sense of belonging pre- and post-diagnosis to minimise the risk of trauma or re-traumatisation.

A Canadian study by Novek and Menec., (2020) involved individuals with YOD, their families and caregivers, and healthcare professionals. The findings supported the creation of a specialised diagnostic pathway for young-onset dementia care. Health professionals working in YOD support services can offer a unique perspective when identifying improvements and are often the key to clear communication (Baptista et al., 2016). Previous research has suggested that participants with dementia who did not feel they had a positive connection with healthcare professionals were less likely to engage with ongoing support services (Koehn et al., 2016). In contrast, individuals who reported having a good rapport and felt listened to would be more likely to accept continued care (Novek and Menec, 2020). A fragmented and confusing pre- and post-diagnostic pathway also creates more barriers to accessing support services. Following potential diagnostic delays due to the complex nature of YOD symptoms, individuals in this study felt the challenges faced by those under 65 years of age should be addressed in family-centred support streams.

Self-worth and purpose can often be measured by experiences of psychological trauma, altering life perspectives and self-esteem (Spytska, 2023). These emotional traits are also affected by the pathway to a diagnosis of YOD (van Vliet et al., 2017). A scoping review by Mayhofer et al., (2018) addressed the challenges faced by individuals with a YOD diagnosis and their families when accessing the proper support. The study employed dyadic interviews with individuals with YOD and their families, as well as individual interviews with health professionals. Those with YOD were noted as 'experts by experience'. When reflecting on the scoping review by Mayrhofer et al., (2017), the group identified some significant findings (Mayrhofer et al., 2018). In particular, the group discussed the negative impact of short-term duration support offerings in YOD services in England. They felt that long-term, continuous services with the same staff would have provided them with a more solid support network to stay in touch with others who offered peer support in similar situations. Accessible social platforms involving those of a similar age and situation were also highlighted as an essential factor in providing post-diagnostic support. In the

second round of discussions, Mayrhofer et al., (2018) asked participants what improvements could be made to shape better support for the UK. Individuals with YOD and their family or caregivers suggested a community go-to 'hub' dedicated to YOD services and connecting local social networks of those affected by YOD. One suggestion was to provide gender-specific support to attend social activities, such as swimming or shopping, to promote independence for a more extended period. The sense of community, building trusting relationships, and compassionate care reported aligns with several TIP that are rooted in TIC (Sweeney et al., 2018). Szczygiel, (2018) highlighted the need for further research applying trauma-informed approaches in care practices from the onset to diagnosis of dementia.

The pre- and post-diagnosis of YOD and support services offering this peer support, building safe relationships, could explore YOD diagnostic support through a trauma-informed lens (Szczygiel, 2018). Additionally, creating a 'hub' would allow family members affected by YOD to also connect as often those with a YOD diagnosis have children under 25 years of age who will need support to release feelings and discuss the challenges they face with young adults in a similar position (Masterson-Algar and Williams, 2020). Mayrhofer et al. (2018) found that health professionals recognised some high-quality support services for YOD, which are fragmented and dependent on regional service providers. The study concluded that lifetime support for individuals living in the community, particularly those affected by YOD, is vital for future research.

Oyebode et al., (2023) interviewed eighteen staff members, including two dementia service commissioners, to understand the pathways needed to create and sustain tailored, quality support services for people with YOD. The data from the study mirrored previous research, where staff felt that those with lived experience of YOD should be involved in developing YOD services and that an evaluation of existing services should be conducted (Fox et al., 2020; Hutchinson et al., 2020; Mayrhofer et al., 2020). The study recognises that finding those living with YOD is a multidisciplinary and complex partnership that must be established through transparent collaboration between organisations. Oyebode et al., (2023) found that peer support among staff members would be an important facilitator in services progressing with more expertise. Having knowledgeable staff members share best practices when supporting those affected by YOD was seen as a potential benefit. As all participants in the study were already part of a YOD service, the study suggested that future services should begin

with an experienced member of staff collaborating with individuals with YOD and their families to develop new services. Using CASP, the relevance of the study was confirmed for exploring the development of services. The aims were clearly stated and the methodology successfully captured professional insight.

The following section considers trauma-informed approaches to dementia.

2.6.3 Trauma-Informed Approach

There is a paucity of evidence where the impact of trauma influences the experience of dementia, and the potential of using TIC with people with dementia is considered. Prolonged exposure to stress and a single traumatic event can reactivate historical traumatic memories, resulting in frequent intrusive recollections (Cheung, Garber, and Bryant, 2015). Evidence suggests older adults who are hospitalised in-patients who have experienced a historical traumatic event, particularly those with a diagnosis of dementia, often experience stress and distress (Sampson et al., 2014). Those with historical trauma are at greater risk of future trauma, and the risk of experiencing trauma increases with age, creating a double vulnerability (Muskett, 2014; Cations et al., 2021). A study by Craftsman et al. (2019), using a qualitative descriptive and inductive approach, set in a care home, focused on the experiences of nursing assistants (n=9) providing care for residents with dementia who had historical traumatic experiences such as the Holocaust. Nursing assistants accepted that trauma triggers may be spontaneous and highlighted the importance of person-centred care, knowing residents' life stories and training for staff to recognise potential trauma triggers (Craftsman et al., 2019).

Although this sample of nine participants was small, it does provide insight into the reality of a professional carer for a PLWD with previous trauma, which is valuable, and further research is critical to understanding how delivering TIC can support adults with previous trauma to reduce adverse events or the reactivation of trauma, particularly when co-occurring with dementia (Couzner et al., 2022). Additionally, Craftsman et al., (2019) do not take into consideration survivors with a diagnosis of dementia who are living in the community and would be more relevant to this research had the sample included carers who support YOD than those solely with advanced dementia. Throughout the literature review, there is a paucity of evidence relating to

psychological trauma and YOD forming a bidirectional relationship and the impact TIP could have.

van Vliet et al., (2017) considered meaningful engagement in daily living with YOD to support positive coping strategies. Eighteen people with YOD and twenty-one informal caregivers participated in focus group interviews; four main themes were identified: (1) staying engaged, (2) loss in daily life, (3) coping and adaptation, and (4) external support. The four themes for participants post-diagnosis communicated a clear need to retain a continued sense of usefulness after the diagnosis. A feeling of 'usefulness' was found in work-related interventions, participating in enjoyable activities, having a sense of autonomy and retaining responsibility for household activities. This can lead to a sense of empowerment, which is a TIP. When this is lacking, it may create psychological suffering or trauma for both those with a YOD diagnosis and carers (van Vliet et al., 2010). Again, when a sense of purpose and identity is questioned, trauma or re-traumatisation can develop (Berman, Montgomery and Ratner, 2020). While the findings of the study may not differ from the experiences of those diagnosed with late-onset dementia (Steeman et al., 2006), it may be more prevalent in YOD because individuals are under 65 years old as their diagnosis may impact employment status, intimate relationships, and social expectations (Clemerson, Walsh, and Isaac, 2013). The use of focus groups allowed for rich, interactive data collection, and ethical considerations were addressed. The inclusion of both individuals with YOD and their informal caregivers strengthened the depth of the findings, enhancing credibility and transferability. Overall, the study contributes meaningfully to understanding how engagement and identity preservation can support trauma-informed approaches in YOD care.

Following a document analysis of UK health policies and interviews with healthcare staff, Emsley et al. (2022) found that there is no UK or National Health Service-wide strategy to implement trauma-informed (TI) approaches in healthcare services. Policies included were all written by the UK government, as well as multiple sectors and service users. Encouragingly, Scotland and Wales had a clear nationwide strategy, but this was found to be fragmented in England. When TI care is delivered by well-informed staff, it can increase patient engagement and retention in support services, leading to improved emotional well-being (Dawson et al., 2021). This approach could transform key issues raised by participants in the study by Mayrhofer

et al. (2018) if a TI pathway were adapted for those affected by YOD and the diagnostic journey. However, no literature has investigated this. Interview analysis revealed a shared opinion among participants that a UK-wide vision for how TI approaches are delivered in the broader context of public health should be a permanent approach used in healthcare systems (Emsley et al., 2022). There was a clear need to evaluate and raise awareness of how TI care can transform services and support approaches. The prevalence and causes of YOD are diverse, with a complex aetiology (Withall et al., 2014), and many risks associated with YOD can be linked to poorer mental and physical health, which can be the direct result of experiencing trauma (Magruder, McLaughlin and Elmore Borbon, 2017). The idea of a nationally recognised TI approach being specifically implemented in YOD health services, as suggested by Emsley et al. (2022), could create a successful TI pathway in YOD diagnosis to support individuals who experience daily life anxiety and the feeling of constant loss (Johannessen et al., 2018).

2.6.4 Life-altering Diagnosis

Receiving a diagnosis of YOD can be compared to the literature around life-altering diagnoses, including a cancer diagnosis, in several ways. A life-limiting diagnosis, such as terminal cancer, can often increase the risk of trauma or traumatisation (Ganzel, 2018). Both can lead to anxiety, sleep disturbances, emotional distress, and a decline in quality of life (QoL) (Bergerot et al., 2013). Gori et al., (2021) recruited 154 individuals from Italian cancer research associations to explore how resilience and coping strategies can be implemented in individuals diagnosed with cancer. All participants had received a diagnosis of cancer and were currently at various stages of treatment (i.e. undergoing treatment or cancer survivor). The study revealed that younger participants displayed reduced resilience following diagnosis, resulting in adverse trauma effects and heightened avoidance behaviours, such as withdrawing from support systems and denying their situation, due to younger participants being more likely to experience neuroticism. The research question was clearly focused, and the methodology was appropriate for exploring psychological responses to diagnosis. Ethical considerations were addressed, and the sample size was sufficient to support generalisability. However, the study did not fully explore the role of external support systems or cultural factors that may influence coping and resilience. Despite this, the

findings offer valuable insights into how age and personality traits may influence trauma responses, which can be cautiously applied to YOD populations.

The parallels identified with Bergerot et al. (2013) concerning dementia and cancer diagnoses suggest that the findings of this study could also be relevant to dementia. Post-traumatic growth (PTG) was present when individuals showed a positive attitude during treatment, especially in cancer survivors. However, PTG is harder to link to dementia due to the disease's progressive nature and cognitive decline (Geugten and Goossensen, 2019). Some cancers can be treated effectively involving surgery, chemotherapy and radiotherapy; however, dementia has no cure; therefore, emotional distress may be acute (Kao, Yeh and Chen, 2023). Individuals with cancer are more likely to complete advanced care plans than those with a dementia diagnosis, improving end-of-life care (Gotanda et al., 2022). While those with a diagnosis of dementia are unlikely to experience PTG, it is possible that a model providing positive coping strategies centred around TIP for family and carers could minimise trauma and re-traumatisation (Jackson, Maurin and Fedio, 2024; Li et al., 2020). A diagnosis of Parkinson's disease leads to a progressive cognitive and physical decline, and efforts to learn about the individual and adopt a trauma-informed approach may not promote PTG but can reduce the risk of traumatisation (Ricks-Aherne, Wallace and Kusmaul, 2020).

2.7 Conclusion

From the literature reviewed, the diagnostic pathway of YOD can include a potential risk of trauma or re-traumatisation. Before, during and after diagnosis can result in heightened stress due to the lengthy timeframe. A YOD diagnosis can bring complex needs for individuals and their families. While current literature considers individual elements of TIP, there is a lack of research on how a trauma-informed pathway can be collectively applied to the diagnostic journey of YOD. A diagnosis of YOD can lead to a sense of loss, anxiety, stress and cognitive decline. These are all elements which can trigger trauma or re-traumatisation. Individuals with other life-altering diseases can experience empowerment through trauma-informed practice. This study aims to explore how trauma-informed practice can influence and improve the diagnostic pathway of YOD. While the Scottish Government (2021) promote the use of TIP, there is a lack of evidence surrounding its application to the YOD population.

This research will specifically consider how TIP can be directly applied to the YOD diagnostic pathway.

Chapter 3: Methodology

3.1 Introduction

This chapter outlines the study's aims and objectives, followed by a justification of the methodology and a discussion of the population, sampling, ethical considerations, and the philosophical underpinnings of the approach employed. It outlines, discusses, and justifies the research design. Trauma-informed approaches were woven into the design of this study. The Records Management Protocol at the University of the West of Scotland was followed.

3.2 Aims and Objectives

3.2.1 Aims

This project aimed to investigate the potential for a trauma-informed pathway through the diagnosis of dementia for people under 65 years of age.

3.2.2 Objectives

- To understand the diagnostic experiences of people with young-onset dementia and their families
- To explore how trauma-informed principles are applied in the diagnostic experience
- To explore the potential of how a trauma-informed framework can improve the diagnostic experience for people with young-onset dementia.

3.3 Research Philosophy

3.3.1 Paradigms

The positivist paradigm is grounded in the belief that a single, objective reality exists, and researchers aim to test hypotheses by collecting and comparing data (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2019, p. 144). This approach is commonly linked to quantitative research, where consistent variables are used to develop an impartial understanding (Weaver & Olson, 2006). In contrast, qualitative research is typically aligned with the interpretivist paradigm, which acknowledges the researcher's subjective role in interpreting the world through existing knowledge and personal understanding (Goldkuhl, 2012).

3.3.2 Quantitative research

Quantitative research primarily focuses on gathering numerical data or samples and applying statistical methods to test hypotheses, explore theories, and identify emerging patterns (Zyphur & Pierides, 2017; Ali & Bhaskar, 2016). This approach is typically grounded in the positivist paradigm and is commonly employed in methodologies such as experimental, quasi-experimental, and randomized controlled trials (Kivunja & Kuyini, 2017). However, as Queirós, Faria, and Almeida (2017) note, quantitative research has limitations, including challenges in controlling variables and its inability to capture participants' emotions and behaviours. Zyphur and Pierides (2017) further critique the approach for being repetitive and for overlooking participants' values and concerns, while Bauer et al. (2021) highlight its lack of intersectionality, particularly in health and social care contexts. Despite these criticisms, quantitative research within a positivist framework can reinforce existing knowledge by supporting previous findings. When designed effectively, it enables the measurement of phenomena on a large scale (Park, Konge & Artino, 2020), provided the study design is robust, inclusive, and far-reaching (Walker et al., 2019).

3.3.3 Qualitative research

Qualitative research considers the *nature of phenomena*, using methods such as semi-structured interviews or focus groups. These are assessed by the researcher using sampling and coding strategies to enhance the quality of the data collected (Busetto, Wick, & Gumbinger, 2020). Qualitative researchers typically explore a

research question that focuses on how a person felt or their experience, which is then collated and analysed to identify emerging themes through a systematic approach (Seers, 2012).

Semi-structured interviews are a common method in qualitative research. A well-known advantage of this method is the relationship formed between participant and researcher, allowing questions to evolve throughout the interview and enabling deeper insights (Galletta, 2013, p.73). Another strength of semi-structured interviews is their flexibility and adaptability, allowing the researcher to respond to participants' experiences and thoughts (Kallio et al., 2016).

However, McCambridge, Witton, and Elbourne (2014) argue that this can also be a disadvantage, as participants may experience the *Hawthorne effect*—a heightened awareness of being studied—which can lead them to alter their behaviour or responses out of concern for being judged. Nevertheless, Maher and Dertadian (2017) suggest that this is intrinsic to qualitative research, which seeks to explore complex human behaviours.

Qualitative research also allows for robust data collection through various formats, such as audio diaries, which can sustain participants' engagement and yield rich, detailed data (Crozier & Cassell, 2015). Thematic analysis is frequently used to help researchers identify key themes emerging from the data. This process can be conducted in stages to develop a deep understanding of participants' responses (Lester, Cho, & Lochmiller, 2020).

Overall, qualitative research can produce rich and robust data (Crozier & Cassell, 2015) and offers significant insights, particularly when addressing knowledge gaps in public health (Doyle et al., 2020).

3.3.4 Qualitative descriptive research

Qualitative descriptive research (QDR) is often utilised in early researchers' qualitative projects, as it provides novice researchers with a straightforward platform to collect data on descriptive experiences and individual perceptions of phenomena (Sandelowski, 2010; Colorafi and Evans, 2016). It is frequently employed in research aimed at addressing clinical issues and providing findings that can directly contribute to improving healthcare experiences (Chafe, 2017). A deeper understanding of the

experiences of individuals with YOD and their families within the context of dementia diagnosis processes is achieved. The study employed interpretive and critical perspectives, embracing multiple and subjective experiences (Doyle et al., 2020). QDR is not without criticism. Some have argued that it lacks consistency due to excessive flexibility (Vaismoradi, Turunen, and Bondas, 2013). However, when applied in healthcare research, the diversity and flexibility of the approach can successfully illuminate the experiences of those with lived experience and healthcare professionals in realistic settings (Doyle et al., 2020).

A suitable type of analysis for research data depends on whether a specific question is being addressed (deductive) or if the researcher anticipates that research questions will emerge as the data is analysed (inductive) (Braun and Clarke, 2006). As deductive approaches have an already established framework, the data are analysed with the assumption that key concepts will be present in the data (Bradley, Curry, and Devers, 2007). Oosterveld-Vlug et al., (2013) is an example of a study using both QDR and a deductive approach involving those with lived experience addressing an under-represented public health issue. A deductive process utilises current literature to inform the research topic, resulting in clear research aims and objectives (Azungah, 2018). Data can be reviewed and coded with aspects fitting within the chosen matrix (Sandström et al., 2015).

An inductive approach follows bottom-up reasoning, starting with specific observations and leading to general conclusions (Bergdahl and Berterö, 2014). Inductive analysis can support the researcher in gaining a deeper understanding of the data if there is a need to go beyond the deductive approaches already applied (Sandström et al., 2015). The project used an inductive approach to data gathering, moving to a deductive approach for data analysis and findings development. This inductive-deductive reasoning is supported Creswell et al., (2013).

3.4 Sampling

Purposive sampling involves identifying individuals who possess rich lived experiences or in-depth knowledge of a particular phenomenon (Palinkas et al., 2015). It works well with QDR as participants are recruited based on specific criteria to support the study's objectives in understanding phenomena (Bradshaw, Atkinson and Doody, 2017). It was chosen for this study because it supports the approach of

achieving a manageable amount of data for a project with a shorter timeline (Ames, Glenton, and Lewin, 2019). It also enables the researcher to select participants who are suitable to share their experiences, resulting in rich data and findings (Fraenkel et al., 2015). Alternative approaches were considered, such as convenience sampling, which involves selecting readily available participants (Golzar, Noor, and Tajik, 2022). However, this approach does not focus on characteristics that would enhance the research study, but rather on participants who are easily accessible for data collection (Islam and Aldaihani, 2021).

3.5 Semi-structured interviews

Using semi-structured interviews in qualitative research can enhance the depth of data gathered, which can be assessed and coded by a researcher to identify themes relevant to the research questions (Busetto, Wick and Gumbinger, 2020). The rapport built between the participant and researcher can further enrich data collection in studies because the dialogue exchange allows for a structured and flexible approach (Galletta, 2013, p. 73). This study will optimise the afforded flexibility, ensuring an adaptable base for the researcher (Kallio et al., 2016). Semi-structured interviews can capture firsthand experiences and perceptions of those with lived experience (Maher and Dertadian, 2017). This could be a drawback, as experiences shared in this way may influence responses due to the awareness of being observed (McCambridge, Witton, and Elbourne, 2014). However, the study does not consider the researcher's crucial role in semi-structured interviews. Verbal and nonverbal communication can help researchers identify authentic responses (Coleman, 2022). Researchers can seek further clarification from participants using techniques such as repetition and paraphrasing (Grey, 2018).

3.6 Framework analysis

A framework approach is a matrix where all participants in the study are included in a row, with the selected themes heading each column (Kiernan and Hill, 2018). A researcher can analyse raw data and attribute elements to the established themes (Ritchie and Lewis, 2003; Furber, 2010). A framework analysis is often used in managing data, analysing and identifying themes in qualitative healthcare research studies (Hackett and Strickland, 2019). Using a framework approach in QDR can summarise and condense large amounts of transcribed data; the matrix format is

straightforward and supports the researcher in identifying evidence that aligns with proposed themes (Gale et al., 2013). Framework analysis by Ritchie and Spencer, (1994) incorporates five stages carried out by the researcher –

- (1) data familiarisation
- (2) identifying a thematic framework
- (3) indexing all study data against the framework
- (4) charting to summarise the indexed data
- (5) mapping and interpretation

It provides a platform for small-scale studies, where data can be intensively analysed to develop researcher insights and findings (Klingberg, Stalmeijer, and Varpio, 2023). The researcher adopted an a priori framework based on the five trauma-informed principles by NES.

3.7 Methods

3.7.1 Research Design

This study used qualitative descriptive research (QDR), as outlined by Doyle (2020). This healthcare research design, which explores subjective experiences, sought a deeper understanding of the experiences of people with young-onset dementia and their families in the context of dementia diagnosis processes. Both interpretive and critical perspectives embrace multiple and subjective experiences.

3.7.2 Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for the study was submitted to the UWS Ethical Review Manager and NHS Integrated Research Application System (IRAS). The researcher attended a virtual research ethics committee meeting for the IRAS application, which was a valuable experience as a first-time researcher. The application was successful following two minor changes. Both applications were approved.

Throughout the project, the researcher has worked closely with a Senior Research and Development Facilitator within an NHS Health Board.

A diagnosis of dementia can be a stressful and unknown time, which can be directly linked to developing post-traumatic stress (Dunham et al., 2019); therefore, the

researcher was mindful of potential feelings of distress developing from questions asked throughout the interview when remembering and reflecting on their experience. All participants had full capacity and could withdraw from the project at any time without providing a reason. Ensuring participants had full capacity for the project's duration involved a multidisciplinary approach to verify that consent had not changed, which included collaboration with health professionals, family caregivers, and the individual. Family and loved ones are significant support in times of stress and challenges and can also encourage empowerment (Hart et al., 2020); therefore, all participants were welcome to bring someone they trusted to the interview. The participants were given the option to attend the interview independently if they preferred.

Carrying out best practice when engaging with those affected by dementia, the Dementia Engagement and Empowerment Project (DEEP) 'Collecting the Views of People with Dementia' (DEEP, 2023), UWS ethical guidelines and Nursing and Midwifery Council code of conduct were all adhered to. This was carried out in various aspects of the project, including phone and email pre- and post-meetings to support individuals in preparing and reflecting on the interview, ensuring a quiet space at the participant's chosen location, and providing participants with project updates and findings in easy-to-understand language.

The researcher conducted a debriefing via phone call within 1-2 days of the interview, allowing participants to reflect on the interview and discuss any aspects they felt embarrassed or upset about. The researcher adapted the debrief call to be a relaxed conversation tailored to the participant's needs. Gatekeepers of the project provide additional support to all participants throughout the project and beyond. Stakeholders remained available to meet individually with participants and NHS staff for a debriefing should they require further support and reflection.

The researcher considered that the ability to consent may change throughout the project; therefore, the researcher constantly verbally revisited the consent form before any new conversations occurred. The researcher, a registered mental health nurse, used their training in recognising potential distress throughout the interview. In this instance, the researcher would organically draw the interview to a close to minimise further distress. The Dementia Nurse/AHP Consultant (NHS) supported the

researcher in referring participants to the appropriate health professional when any disclosures or distress were raised during the interviews.

3.7.3 Study population

Purposive sampling enabled the researcher to focus in-depth on a small sample, supporting each phase of the project (Palinkas et al., 2015). While purposive sampling is based on the subjective selection of the researcher, inclusion criteria aimed to recruit people under 65 years old with a diagnosis of young onset dementia with full capacity; however, this was not limited to male/female, subtypes of dementia or ethnicity to ensure diverse perspectives and experiences were represented, as diverse participants have a potential to offer rich knowledge to this developing project (Campbell et al., 2020).

A total of nine people participated in the study. There were three people with a diagnosis of YOD, three family/carers and three health professionals. The findings represent seven interviews.

Figure 1. Study population and location of interviews

Participant	Location			
	Online via Microsoft Teams	Home	UWS University Campus	Place of Work
YOD	1			
Family/carer			1	
Dyads (made up of 1x carer and 1x YOD)		1	1	
Health professionals				3
Total	1	1	2	3

Boddy (2016) suggests that smaller sample sizes in qualitative research can generate deep insight in semi-structured interviews, where data saturation can be evident after six in-depth interviews and strongly evident after twelve in-depth interviews.

3.7.4 PPIE Involvement

The researcher met with members of the Scottish Working Dementia Group and National Dementia Carers Action Network to discuss potential data gathering, enabling strategies, and risks. The advice from the members of the forum was as follows –

- Avoid personal questions to minimise potential distress. Open questions will allow the participant to lead the conversation. This will allow the participants to share what they feel comfortable with and ensure they feel safe.
- Ask participants to 'explain in your own words'.
- Do not assume anything about the participant, such as where they are on the diagnostic pathway.
- Be mindful of the 'endpoint'. Once you feel you cannot go any further with the question, then move on to the next.
- Use 'easy-to-understand' language.
- A presentation/seminar on findings to the group would be appreciated.
- Use the support of your supervisors as much as you can.
- When disseminating the project findings, ensure something is provided in Word so members/participants can use the read-aloud function.

The advice offered by this focus group was integrated into the project's methods. The research ensured that participant information sheets and consent forms were in an easy-to-understand format. The interview questions were open-ended, allowing participants to share the information they felt comfortable with.

3.7.5 Recruitment Strategy

Recruitment for the project utilised networks already established by the Alzheimer Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice (ASCPP) team, including NHS Health Board, Alzheimer Scotland (AS), National Dementia Carers Action Network (NDCAN) and Scottish Dementia Research Consortium (SDRC). Specific support from YOD

Dementia networks in Scotland was in place, with gatekeeper support for recruitment and participation. The researcher established connections with all networks via email and Microsoft Teams meetings, discussing the project as part of the development process.

The project has two gatekeepers: the Active Voices Lead and Alzheimer Scotland Dementia Nurse/AHP Consultant (NHS Lanarkshire). The researcher prepared a recruitment video, which was sent separately to both gatekeepers via email. The Active Voices Lead sent the recruitment video to relevant mailing lists to support the recruitment process of those diagnosed with young-onset dementia under 65 years old at the time of diagnosis. This included carers and caring dyads, as those diagnosed with young-onset dementia could identify a family member or carer to participate.

The recruitment video can be accessed on the following link or QR code:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KC3FzbWevzc>

3.7.6 Staff Recruitment

The Dementia Nurse/AHP Consultant (NHS Lanarkshire) and the manager of the Young Onset Dementia Service team in NHS Lanarkshire will support the recruitment of NHS Lanarkshire staff by identifying appropriate staff groups directly involved with the diagnostic process of young-onset dementia.

3.7.7 YOD, carer and carer dyad recruitment

NHS Lanarkshire staff groups who are directly involved with the diagnostic process of young-onset dementia sent the project's recruitment video to appropriate caseloads with a diagnosis of young-onset dementia under 65 years old at the time of diagnosis. This included carers and caring dyads, as those diagnosed with young-onset dementia

may identify a family member or carer to participate. The manager of the Young Onset Dementia Service team in the NHS health board supported the NHS staff in doing this. The Dementia Nurse/AHP Consultant (NHS) sent the recruitment video to relevant mailing lists to support the recruitment of carers and caring dyads, which included people with young-onset dementia.

All email communication by gatekeepers and NHS staff was carried out using the 'Bcc' field function to ensure recipients were kept private and invisible to others.

The researcher's contact details were provided in the recruitment video, and potential interested participants were asked to respond to the researcher directly via the email address provided. If the researcher received an email from a potential interested participant, a participant information sheet, a prompt sheet, a data protection information sheet, and a consent form were sent to the participant. This helped them decide if they wanted to be part of the project. The researcher invited family carers to participate as individuals or invited the person they cared for to be interviewed as a dyad or as an individual, if they consented to participation. If the participant chose to participate in the study, the researcher would ask them to complete and sign the consent form, which would then be sent to them. The researcher arranged to meet with the participant or dyad at their preferred time and location.

All participants were given a Participant Information Pack with the following –

1. Participant Information Sheet
2. Data Management and Protection Information Sheet
3. Prompt Sheet
4. Trauma-Informed Principles Information Sheet
5. Consent Form

Appendices 5, 6, and 7 show each variation of the Participant Information Pack, depending on the participant.

3.7.8 Data collection method

The approach facilitated a person and family-centred perspective, with information collected using semi-structured interviews. Interviews were conducted with individuals

or dyads (comprising individuals with YOD and their family caregivers) who had experienced a diagnosis of YOD, as well as with professionals involved in the diagnosis, in various locations of the participants' choice. Participants chose the location of their interview and were allowed to bring a family member or caregiver, both of whom were encouraged to facilitate successful communication in dementia care (Kjallman Alm, Hellzen, and Norbergh, 2013). Changes in familiarity can be particularly challenging for individuals living with dementia (Margot-Cattin et al., 2021). Therefore, all participants in this project chose the location where they would like to be interviewed. Research demonstrates that people with dementia are more likely to engage when they feel comfortable and familiar with their surroundings (Gaber et al., 2019). Furthermore, adopting a person-centred approach and 'recognition of client personhood' were essential practices for the researcher working with participants of a project diagnosed with dementia (Riachi, 2017).

3.7.9 Phases of the study

The research had two data generation phases: (1) data generation with individuals and/or family/carers who have experienced a YOD diagnosis, and (2) Individual interviews with staff involved in diagnostic processes, e.g. memory clinic or community mental health teams.

Dyadic interviews were conducted with the person diagnosed with dementia and another individual who provided an additional perspective on the dementia pathway experience, such as a family member, caregiver, or close supporter.

3.7.10 A trauma-informed approach

The researcher adopted a trauma-informed approach to data gathering, utilising the five principles of trauma-informed practice – safety, trustworthiness, choice, collaboration, and empowerment, which prioritise participants' well-being (Scottish Government, 2021). As a registered mental health nurse, the researcher recognises that a trauma-informed approach is essential in promoting safety and delivering comprehensive care (Stokes et al., 2017). Participants were given the choice of where they wanted to conduct the interview, and rapport was established before the interviews, prior to the meeting, as the researcher introduced themselves via phone call and email before the interview date. This was an attempt to promote a sense of psychological and emotional safety and trust prior to interviews. Family and loved ones

are significant sources of support in times of stress and challenge, and can also encourage empowerment (Hart et al., 2020); therefore, all participants were welcome to bring someone they trusted to the interview. The participants were given the option to attend the interview independently if they preferred. Data collection did not commence during the introductory calls, which were intended solely to introduce the researcher to the participant. The researcher ensured that the conversation did not cover aspects of data collection. The principles of trauma-informed practice supported the researcher in establishing a safe and secure environment with the participant and building a therapeutic relationship that aligns with everyone's story, which are fundamental concepts in nursing care (Peplau, 1991).

Using a deductive approach, trauma-informed principles provided the theoretical framework for the study across the researcher's actions in arranging and conducting interviews, analysis, and dissemination.

3.8 Data analysis

3.8.1 Framework analysis

The researcher followed the five stages of Ritchie and Spencer's (1994) framework analysis, with one stage amended due to the use of an already defined framework. The analysis was conducted through a trauma-informed and co-productive lens, ensuring that the voices of participants were central to interpretation and that the process upheld principles of safety, trust, and empowerment. Continual reflexivity, both individually and in collaboration with the supervisory team, was maintained to support transparency, rigour, and ethical sensitivity throughout the process (Doyle, 2020).

Familiarisation with the Interview

Interviews were recorded using an audio recording device and transcribed via Microsoft Word's transcription feature. To immerse in the data, the researcher listened to the recordings during transcription, allowing for correction of errors and deeper engagement with participant narratives. All audio files and transcripts were handled in accordance with the UWS Data Protection Code of Practice, stored securely on password-protected systems with authentication safeguards.

Each interview was listened to twice, once during transcription and again during a separate reflective session. During the second listening, the researcher made analytical and reflective notes, remaining 'data-near' to ensure that participant voices were honoured and accurately represented. This stage was approached with sensitivity to the emotional content of the interviews, recognising the potential impact of discussing dementia diagnoses and related experiences.

Coding Framework

An a priori framework was adopted, guided by the five trauma-informed principles: safety, choice, collaboration, empowerment, and trustworthiness (NHS Education for Scotland, 2024). This framework provided a structured yet flexible approach to exploring how these principles were reflected in the YOD diagnostic pathway. Sub-themes were identified inductively to ensure that emerging insights were not constrained by the predefined categories, allowing participant experiences to shape the analysis meaningfully (Miles, Huberman, & Saldana, 2020; McGowan, Powell, & French, 2020).

An Excel document was used to organise the data, with participants listed in the first row and each trauma-informed principle represented in separate columns. An 'Additional Notes' section captured emerging themes and reflections, supporting a co-productive interpretation of the data.

Coding

Codes were applied through repeated listening and close reading of transcripts. The researcher used reflective notes and the established framework to identify relevant data, ensuring that coding remained grounded in participant narratives and aligned with trauma-informed values.

Charting

Data were extracted and categorised using the Excel framework, integrating analytical and reflective notes. This process was conducted with attention to emotional nuance and participant agency, ensuring that the charting stage did not reduce complex experiences to simplistic categories.

Mapping and Interpretation

The final stage involved exploring relationships between themes and principles. This interpretive process was guided by trauma-informed and co-productive values, recognising the interconnectedness of participant experiences and the broader diagnostic context. The researcher engaged in collaborative reflection with the supervisory team to ensure that interpretations were ethically sound, inclusive, and representative of the lived experiences shared.

3.8.2 Data Management and Data Protection

The project was supervised by experienced qualitative researchers from UWS, and with their guidance and support, the researcher was committed to ethical compliance and protecting participants' integrity. In line with The Declaration of Helsinki (World Medical Association, 2022), the research team protected the privacy and confidentiality of the personal information of research participants. The researcher followed the UWS GDPR protocol. It maintained anonymity in the dissemination of research findings. Interviews took place in a relaxed environment free from interruption, where sensitive information could be shared confidentially. Each participant was allocated a code to ensure anonymity throughout transcriptions and direct quotes. Coding for participants with young-onset dementia, family members/carers, and NHS staff was coded separately to ensure a clear distinction between them. The codes were used when quoting and referencing participants, and participant codes were stored separately from the anonymised interview transcripts.

Data collection was password protected, and only the researcher and two project supervisors had access to it. The researcher used the secure transcribing platform on Microsoft Word to transcribe the audio. The researcher complied with all UWS Data Protection regulations and the NHS Code of Confidentiality (Department of Health and Social Care, 2003).

Personal data is stored on UWS secure systems. This is password-protected and stored securely by UWS secure systems following the UWS Protocol for the Use of Cloud Storage.

Any written notes, audio recording devices, and consent forms were stored in a locked steel file box. The researcher is the only one with the keys to access this. When transcribing the data, the researcher was in a secure environment at the UWS

campus, with no interruptions, and used headphones while listening to the audio recordings.

On completion of the project, all data recorded in all formats were uploaded to the UWS research repository in line with the UWS Research Data Management Procedure.

The UWS Protocol for the Use of Cloud Storage and the Research Data Management Procedure were familiarised by the researcher.

3.8.3 Dissemination

The dissemination of research can enhance practice among healthcare professionals and influence further research and policymaking (Tabak et al., 2017). The researcher is fully committed to ensuring the successful dissemination of the project to all those involved and those interested in the research. The data will be presented to various stakeholders in several ways. Presentation of findings will include a condensed report, verbal and visual presentations delivered in-person and via Microsoft Teams, a poster presentation, attending relevant conferences, and meeting with all relevant stakeholders to receive feedback on the findings. Stakeholders include participants, Alzheimer Scotland, the University of the West of Scotland, the National Dementia Carers Action Network (NDCAN), the Scottish Dementia Working Group (SDWG), NHS Lanarkshire, Scottish Dementia Research Consortium (SDRC), and any other stakeholder deemed necessary.

All dissemination methods will uphold confidentiality and respect for participants and NHS Boards, who will remain anonymous throughout. The process will be guided by principles of transparency, choice, and cultural sensitivity, ensuring that dissemination is not only informative but also empowering and respectful of the emotional impact that research findings may have.

Chapter 4: Findings

4.1 Content

This chapter presents the study's findings, which address the study's aim of understanding the diagnostic experience of people with young-onset dementia and their families and investigating how a trauma-informed framework can potentially improve their diagnostic experience. The five principles of trauma-informed care serve as the framework for presenting the findings, with supporting direct quotations from the study participants. The findings are reported under two headings; 'Participants with lived experience' incorporating those with a diagnosis of YOD and carers of those with YOD and 'Staff' who are professionals directly involved in the YOD diagnostic pathway.

4.2 Overview of findings

The findings illuminate how people with YOD and family carers in this study felt that before, during, and after the diagnostic process, they felt physically and emotionally unsafe. Fear of the unknown, multiple losses of confidence in roles and daily tasks, and inconsistencies in support meant a lack of safety before diagnosis. Without the foundation of safety before diagnosis, collaboration, choice, and empowerment were negatively affected throughout the whole diagnostic process. Healthcare staff recognised the need for trauma-informed principles. Due to funding restrictions and extended waiting times, support was often limited to 1-year post-diagnosis. While this was helpful for people with YOD and family carers, it did not fully meet their complex needs.

4.3 Interviews

4.3.1 Safety

Participants with lived experience

There was a clear feeling of diminishing physical and emotional safety by both carers and YOD. This was not limited to the start of noticing changes and initial conversations with the doctors, but continued even after a diagnosis with C1, calling the whole diagnostic journey a 'horrible experience'. There was a sense of lack of safety

spreading to all the family and not limited to immediate carers of those with YOD with C1, stating:

'The whole family is struggling' [in reference to carer and adult children], 'my son no longer has a relationship with his dad' and 'I am frightened for the kids [now adults] as they no longer have their dad.' (C1)

The fear of an unknown future created a feeling of dread, which intensified as time moved on. Early post-diagnosis, YOD participants reflected on the fear they felt when describing initial concerns with the development of unknown symptoms with *'constant fog in my head'* (D1 YOD) and *'dense fog in my brain'* (D2 YOD). There was a day when D2 YOD *'couldn't even write my own name'* without knowing why.

For D1 YOD, symptoms of YOD starting during COVID-19 lockdown. This, paired with losing their job, led to feeling *'the isolation being terrible'*, having a significant impact on their mental health. Family members were worried about them and thought they had depression. Physical safety also played a part in the concerns of the participants. Before a diagnosis, the D2 carer discovered that D2 YOD had left the iron on, and the door unlocked. D2 YOD agreed, stating *'everyday tasks became difficult'*. This also became a driving issue. Although it was at different stages of diagnosis, carers felt concerned about road safety from the beginning and felt increasingly unsafe as passengers in the car. YOD participants often kept quiet about their diminishing ability to drive. D1 YOD drove slowly all the time. D2 YOD said they *'started to lose confidence driving'*. Post-diagnosis D1 YOD felt *'everyday tasks like walking the dog is too much'*. C1 recognised that there may be a time when the safety of their spouse is a significant concern. Navigating the progression of the diagnosis for C1 and their family is at the forefront, but added their spouse is *'not unsafe... yet'*.

YOD1 felt a sense of safety when a diagnosis of dementia was finally given. They expressed that

'not returning to work probably affected me more than getting my final diagnosis. Getting my final diagnosis really was a release to the way I was feeling. It was a relief. But at the same time, it was a shock' (YOD1).

C1 noticed how confusing the language used by health professionals, such as 'undemonstrated' and 'brain atrophy', when being told the results of scans. This led the family to go home and Google terms to see what they meant. C1 elaborated on this interaction:

'If you look up brain atrophy [on the internet] it can put you put you down all different roads. It doesn't actually say dementia. The first time I became aware [of dementia] is when he got referred to the young onset dementia team' (C1).

This lack of communication played a significant role in compromising the participant's safety, which is also reflected in the issues of collaboration and trustworthiness. A developing theme is that without safety, the other themes struggle to exist. C1 reflected, saying,

'I'm just devoid of emotion on it [referring to the diagnosis process for her husband]. I just deal with what I have to deal with' (C1).

Thoughts of the future were met with a decreasing feeling of safety. C1 explained:

*If it had been a line in the sand and *Spouse name* had a road accident, could I cope better? Because I would still have fresh memories of what life was life [pre-diagnosis]. It's like a big noose around my neck' (C1)*

Staff

Healthcare staff asserted they promoted safety by providing a transparent service. NHS 1 describes their service as:

'Supporting families pre-diagnostically and post-diagnostically and often preparing families and alerting them that the investigations or any assessments we're doing could result in a dementia diagnosis'. So, we're using the word dementia upfront and being very transparent, making sure people are aware of what they are being tested for'. (NHS 1)

Families often become stressed at the pre-diagnosis stage and are

'most upset at that stage' (NHS 1). 'there's always a bit of hope that it might not be dementia, some families are quite resigned, you can tell they can see what's coming'.

NHS 1 explained they were surprised many families do not take up peer support when they often express,

'No, that's not for me. I just want to deal with it myself and [my] family. I don't want to listen to anybody else's problems (NHS 1).

However, families do change their mind post-diagnosis:

'If they're very anxious, they can take a bit of persuasion, but often they do like the peer support. They do benefit from it, but it's being able to get the peer support of often an issue' (NHS 1).

Establishing important topics after a diagnosis was important for a staff member who asked,

'Have you already done a power of attorney? Are you still driving?' (NHS 2).

Staff used their experience in recognising person-centred support, such as

'You know straight away they need more social support or are struggling with mental health' (NHS 2).

There was evidence of re-traumatisation post-diagnosis. A staff member touched on trauma, saying:

'I feel like it's something we touch on because we see people go back in time and they go back to the trauma that they've had. I had a lady recently who had a terrible childhood. She's been fine with dementia the last couple of years and then recently, she wakes up every morning and feels like she's back there [in her childhood]'. (NHS 2)

NHS 2 credited having the support of family and carers to manage this. Staff highlighted the unique challenges faced by those with YOD:

'a lot of our patients have still got mortgages, young kids at primary school, whereas in an older adult team, you wouldn't get that as much' (NHS 3).

All staff inherited a clear referral system to signpost patients, their families, and their carers to appropriate services. The Alzheimer Scotland café was praised by staff as creating a safe space for those with a diagnosis and their families. A positive aspect of this was that it created long-term support:

'Our services and NHS are time limited, but the social support at Alzheimer Scotland aren't time limited. So, they can go as often as they're able to go' (NHS 1).

However, there was also an awareness of finding the right balance as often individuals 'overshared' (NHS 3) at the café. While this approach is beneficial to some,

'others were coming away quite traumatised by some of the things they were hearing' (NHS 3).

Although the service provided by NHS 1 was limited to one-year post-diagnosis, they explained,

'As long as they need our input, we would keep them on as well despite age. So, if they go over the sixty five age we would keep them on as well if they need stress and distress [support]' (NHS 1).

Staff valued their capacity to do home visits:

'On the whole, the nursing assessments and the OT [occupational therapy] assessments are home visits. And we do it like that because we feel we get so much more from people, much more information from the assessment at a home visit rather than coming to clinic. That can put another pressure on and sometimes it's another barrier for people to try and engage'. (NHS 1)

Staff recognise that the types of assessments they do can provoke anxiety. To mitigate this, staff:

'really try and kind of, you know, break down barriers and get them to relax. Chat beforehand and get to know them a wee bit before we rush through any questions and assessments' (NHS 1).

Continuity was highly rated for its support of the safety of individuals with YOD and their families. NHS 1 explains:

'It is the same named person for the year after diagnosis'. This creates a 'kind of bonding relationship and therapeutic relationship because it's the same person' (NHS1).

This forms a connection with creating trust as well as safety. Staff will often support an individual with feelings of anxiety. Staff usually explore feelings of anxiety with patients and help to identify the triggers. Discussing ways to manage patient anxiety was suggested

'memory management tips, giving them [patients] some diaries, writing things down, white boards, use of technology' (NHS 1).

A staff member felt the wait for patients to see general adult psychiatry, with a further wait to be diverted to a YOD service, was too long. To establish safety from pre-diagnosis, a staff member suggested:

'If that was streamlined, people would be diagnosed a lot quicker. If they are waiting a year or two years, there can be a lot of changes, not understand what is happening. Relationships can be affected. Marriages can break down. It can be a really hard time, and so much harm can be done without getting a diagnosis. (NHS 1)

NHS 3 stated their team often

'spend a lot of time supervising each other whether that's formal or informal, just like a debriefing' (NHS 3).

This approach created a supportive environment for staff, enabling them to frequently reflect on the support they provided and manage any personally challenging experiences.

4.3.2 Trustworthiness

Participants with lived experience

There was a mixture of positive and negative responses relating to trustworthiness and how participants conceptualised trust. C1 generally felt a lack of trust in services and support available to them, reporting,

'support between services was disjointed. No one seemed to know who was doing what'.

D1 carer and D1 YOD expressed trust in individual health professionals. They praised an individual speech therapist for helping set small goals and milestones, and providing practical examples such as starting a memory scrapbook, saying

'milestones were like a project for me. She [speech therapist] did improve my speech by giving me like a project management. A focus' (D1 YOD).

It was clear throughout that all participants, regardless of whether they were carers or YOD, initially had apprehension, but trusted their work colleagues, extended family, and friends. This was reflected in phrases such as

'I didn't want anyone to know. No one at work had to know' (C1),

'I realise now, further into my diagnosis, family and friends are so important' (D1 YOD).

This was echoed by C1, quoting

'the importance of friends, just ensure you keep good friends around you'.

D1 carer said

'we went on holiday. Friends came with us. To be honest, I wouldn't do it on my own. It was in September and it was really fantastic' (D1 carer).

Early both pre- and post-diagnosis, there was an element of masking dementia symptoms by those with YOD. Pre-diagnosis, D2 YOD did not know they had dementia, but they could still tell they were not themselves. They stated

'at work at was at training. I was just about to start filling in the critique sheet. Picked up paper and a pen. I couldn't even make sense of it. Nothing happened [when going to write]. That was scary' (Y2 YOD).

Many symptoms were masked by

'compensating to make sure no one noticed' and 'I would write my pin [for the door at work] under my watch so no one could see' (D2 YOD).

YOD1 did not mention any worries they had about changes pre-diagnosis and instead said

'a few years passed until I mentioned anything'.

Staff

Interpersonal relationships with supervisors and line management were reported to be positive based on one-to-one conversations and professional relationships. It was the wider employment sector input where D2 YOD felt a lack of personhood and felt dismissed following their diagnosis.

'When I had to tell occupational health, they just wrote me off.' (D2 YOD).

There was evident frustration and apprehension about trusting health services. C1 proposed:

'social work will just leave me because I am capable. Does something bad have to happen before I get help?' (C1).

Trust was compromised when healthcare providers sent all D2 YOD health records to the wrong home address. YOD1 had a similar experience with their employer distributing their information, which was never received at the correct place, and

'the employer lost sick notes'.

Creating a trusting environment, both socially and health-related, was valued by all participants. D1, D2, and Y1 all stated that having appointments with the same doctor and consultants was positive and could help build trusted relationships. This notion can also be linked to trustworthiness and collaboration. There was a notable difference between the negative experience highlighted by C1 and the lack of continuity in the clinicians they saw. They stated:

'Why is he being referred to a neurologist? Is it a brain tumour? There was just no more communication other than just saying he has this appointment. It was terrible. The neurologist was from Medicare, I think you call it, which is like bank doctors. There was no continuity ever. Everything just got passed on to somebody else all the time. The whole diagnosis process has been horrific. It's so stressful.' (C1)

NHS 1 talks about creating an inclusive service for individuals with YOD and their families. Themes of trust, choice and collaboration are present here:

'A lot of our role is working with families very closely, signposting family carers to peer support, giving them lots of practical advice and education as well about

the illness or how to manage it. Everybody's different and they're usually really receptive to that, and families are really engaged and keen for any help'. (NHS 1)

Similarly, with safety, all staff valued continuity in building trustworthiness. NHS 1 talked about

'it's hard enough letting somebody at your home without being different people' (NHS 1). Having the same clinician through post-diagnostic support means 'no surprises or strangers coming' (NHS 1).

Staff encourage transparency. NHS 1 explains,

'it's really useful quite often to let people know, to just own it [their diagnosis of YOD] and say, this is what I have. This is how I am dealing with it. This is how you could help me'. (NHS 1).

4.3.3 Choice

Participants with lived experience

Themes of trustworthiness are carried throughout the theme of choice. As well as highlighting the lack of a trusting health care relationship, C1 said there was also a lack of choice in services they had as a support, and the family was confused when old age psychiatry got involved, saying_

'he went to old age psychiatry. So, I am thinking it is his mental health, and he had an assessment done there. He scored very poorly on it. He was told to phone back [later] that day and told not to drive' (C1).

All participants felt that they had a limited choice in selecting options that matched their needs. While it was clear that participants understood why they had different consultants, it created the 'unknown' (C1). A consultant was described as

'literally reading the notes when we walked in [to the appointment] because it was a different doctor from who we had seen prior' (C1).

There was also no choice in when to receive support based on personal preferences. While YOD post-diagnosis services through the NHS were valued, all participants felt that receiving year-long support immediately after diagnosis was not the correct approach. D2 YOD elaborates:

'The whole model has to be restructured. No [not] a postcode lottery. Has to be the right time. The right to choose when to have the support and when it is suited. Need to be told all the options.'

D1 carer explained:

'We had no choice when we received the post-diagnosis support. It was right after the diagnosis, and I would say that was probably our best year when we didn't need it'

C1 echoed this:

'That's us had out year support. Thats it'.

It was clear from the responses that there is a need for flexibility and a demand for increased resources for those with YOD and their families. When given flexible options, positive outcomes were evidenced. D1 YOD was given information on a free exercise class from the speech and language therapist. This was a positive experience for them, and they have continued to do something similar with a paid membership after the event concluded. Similarly, YOD1 found the suggestions made by the consultant to be fun and suited to their interests, such as a singing group. All participants were told about the YOD Alzheimer Scotland (AS) cafes by AS link workers and YOD post-diagnosis NHS services. Out of the six participants with YOD, only one found this suitable. From this part of the interview, it is evident that all participants suggested having the option of peer support. This was conveyed in several ways by participants, ultimately with a shared goal of finding individuals who have a life similar to their own and can offer practical advice, leading to collaboration.

C1 described having someone who still worked, was not retired and had kids early in the 20s would be a good resource to talk to. D1 YOD offered the idea of creating a 'buddy system' where family/carers and those with a YOD diagnosis were 'paired' with families. They suggested

'I don't know what I need until I need it. I've got no idea what is going to be an issue. So I Need somebody to say this might happen and that might happen. And these are the things you can do' (D1 YOD).

They also added

'even meeting for a coffee. So you've got that peer support. But there is nothing formal in place'. and you're building up peer support, which is ultra important.
D1 carer

When two participants could control and accept when they were ready to stop working, there was an accepting attitude towards this. There was also an element of caregiver burden with managing finances:

'I need to continue to work because I have no other choice' C1

Staff

While patients could not choose their allocated key worker, staff ensured they were available even after the standard one-year support model. Patients can choose to re-engage with YOD services:

'people that have been diagnosed have the post diagnostic support, and then they've come back a few years later with stress and distress needing more support' (NHS 2).

This is usually a re-referral through

'people will go to the GP and the GP will come through us, or even Alzheimer Scotland' (NHS 2).

Further support is the choice of the patients, as NHS 2 states:

'it's always just a case of once the PDS [post-diagnostic support] is done, whether it's 12 months, still issues, it's a case of we won't make contact with

you, but if there is anything, just get back in touch with us and we will take it from there' (NHS 2)

Staff provided clear support through signposting, which they felt encouraged patients and families to choose what services they felt would help them. When discussing the unique financial challenges often associated with a YOD diagnosis, NHS 3 stated,

'we would refer them on for anything to do with financial or money problems, just to make sure it removes that one stress'

'They [patients/families] can do like, an income maximisation. They can talk about pensions. They can look at everything that they are entitled to, just to make sure that they're getting everything they can, and that the carers are getting everything they can. (NHS 3)

NHS 2 stated that while all relevant signposting information is given as part of the post-diagnosis support model, there is a clear choice of when patients access support:

'Some people jump straight in and want to get involved in like groups with Alzheimer Scotland or involved with other carers and all these kind of places to sign up to. Whereas some people are just like, I've got a diagnosis. I don't really want to think about it. I'll take the information. I'll put it away. (NHS 2)

Although support groups for those with a YOD diagnosis were visible, a lack of choice for carers accessing support was highlighted:

'Sometimes the carer needs a break, and there's not much out there for taking people [those with a YOD diagnosis] to a group and leaving them so that the carer can get some respite to go and do their own thing for a couple of hours. It's well, the carer has to go, or the carer has to drop them off'. (NHS 2)

In contrast, NHS 3 felt the option for carers to stay in a separate space at an Alzheimer Scotland café created a social support group, stating

'then the family's got their own space' (NHS 3).

Additionally, carer education and stress/distress groups were viewed

'good as well for peer support for carers' (NHS 3).

4.3.4 Collaboration

Participants with lived experience

Participants were often left frustrated by the lack of successful collaboration with health services. The overall experience of C1 exemplified how services were not adapted to involve carers despite investigations of dementia. The C1 spouse was seen alone in appointments, and the first letter C1 received was for a CT scan; however, they have yet to receive the results to this day. C1 spouse attended appointments on their own, but then could not recall the information discussed:

'he got sent for a CT scan. Thereafter, I asked him what happened at the scan? What was the results? What were you going for? What were they looking for? Why? But he didn't know. He couldn't retain it long enough to tell me later'. (C1_

C1 felt like they were in the dark pre-diagnosis, and added:

'only two years after initial problems we were still not thinking dementia. Only when we got a referral through to the young onset dementia team did we realise'.

D1 YOD felt they were 'lucky' because they were being tested for Parkinson's, so it seemed to 'speed up' a diagnosis. D1 carer and YOD also got referred to what seemed like every service available. This led to feeling overwhelmed as they felt like they were

'given too much information in a short period of time. Websites, phone numbers and so on' (D1 carer).

YOD1 'never felt connected' initially to any support services. Still, post-diagnosis, the same YOD link worker and neurologist allowed them to build a collaborative relationship due to consistent and regular meetings. YOD1 stated presently,

'I don't feel unconnected [from support services].

D2 YOD described the diagnosis assessment as a 'mockery' due to COVID-19 restrictions. They recall,

'My dementia assessment was done over the phone. To this day, I do not understand how somebody can do it this way' (Y2 YOD).

The above experience is in opposition to D2YOD where following a lumbar puncture, SPECT scan and MRI, D2 YOD credited the consultant who provided the results of these scans. This was due to the depth of information and explanation provided to the D2 carer and D2 YOD. Quoting the consultant, they said:

'See the shrinkage there? Now, for somebody your age I wouldn't expect that. This is like a hot spot mark. This is the brain cells that are dying. See the ones there [as they pointed to the scan picture]'. They're dead. That colour is dead. This colour [pointing again at a new part of the scan image], here's the living and here is the ones that are in the process of dying' (Y2 YOD).

D2 carer added

'for me, the big thing was that he took time and spoke through it and put everything in context'.

This diagnostic experience was a clear aspect of improving their pathway. Unfortunately, post-diagnosis, their needs were not met. After experiencing initial unpleasant side effects from the medication taken to relieve dementia symptoms, Y2 YOD contacted the nurse assigned to his support for advice. Stating

'I've had sickness. I've had diarrhoea, I've lost 12 pounds in weight in the first week as a consequence' (Y2 YOD).

Quoting the nurse's response to this, D2 YOD said

'you know your body better than me'.

On reflection, D2 YOD recognised they didn't hit it off with the nurse and asked them not to return after a house visit.

From a carer's perspective, C1 spoke positively about the support from their employer. Flexible options such as

'allowed to work from home 2 days a week', having a 'carers passport' and 'pretty much any reasonable request can be accommodated' (C1)

were met with positive responses. Y1 found that collaborating with the AS drop-in café supported positive relationship-building with others living with YOD and opened many opportunities linked to raising awareness of YOD and research. In contrast, after

attending the AS drop-in café, C1, D1 carer/YOD and D2 carer/YOD stated it was unsuitable and did not meet their needs. This was due to feeling out of place, being too young to be there, and having no one in common with them.

Collaborating with researchers and being part of the research were highly valued by participants. While C1 saw the importance of YOD research, they emphasised the need for it to be adapted for those with YOD. After C1's spouse took part in previous research,

'the only thing that kind of fell down with that one was they sent [written] surveys [to complete]' (C1).

This was unsuitable due to reading difficulties. Y2 YOD suggested issues in the post-diagnosis support structure, as there are minimal follow-up appointments with consultants. Adding this leads to

'not having people for research because we're not inviting them back' (Y2 YOD).

Staff

It was clear in the responses from staff that collaboration with patients and families was a highly rated quality of the post-diagnosis support provided. There was a sense of ensuring the correct information and advice was given to the right people. NHS 1 explains that support is about

'being collaborative with the patient and carers, trying to work out what is going to be useful, but what isn't going to work'. Meaningful goal setting was often used to establish

'what is important to them [patient and family]' (NHS 1).

Working collaboratively with wider services supported staff to find the best support for individuals. NHS 3 stated,

'if we felt like somebody would be more suitable to their team' they would work together to establish what resources would be accessed for who.

Working collaboratively to provide social and peer support was lacking. NHS 1 elaborates:

'The one big thing with young onset dementia is the lack of social support. Social work will be the first to admit that, and there really isn't the talk about self-directed support budgets. That's not very accessible for people either. So the whole social and I think it's probably the same throughout all of mental health, but especially young onset dementia'. (NHS 1)

This is echoed by NHS 3:

'I think the biggest change or lack of support is social work support in accessing personal care, daycare that's specific for that person's need'.

While support through the NHS can be 'time-limited,' NHS 1 valued third-sector organisations for long-term patient support. Building on elements associated with safety, continuity of NHS services was highlighted as an essential aspect of collaboration. This can be seen in the value staff put on having a

'named person for the year after diagnosis' (NHS 1).

Tailoring support was viewed as a crucial part of collaboration. All staff spoke of individual cases, generalising how flexible support can be. NHS 3 gives an example:

'We've also got resources for young carers and try to give them as much information as we can at their level. And we've also got resources for like, younger children, say, like young grandchildren that maybe don't understand what's happening to their Grandpa, why they can't remember their name, so we've ordered books for them that are pitched at their level. (NHS 3)

NHS 3 spoke about the differences in what was provided depending on where a patient lives:

'The difference between councils is another big gap. So, what's offered on one council is massively different to what's offered in others' (NHS 3).

It was noted that the importance of staff recognising what individuals needed and whether further signposting was required. NHS 3 explain:

'Diagnostic information, like this, is part of the illness. This comes from medicine. No, this is dementia. You need to go to the doctor for this. You need

to go to social work for this. You need to come to us for this. You need to go back to your doctor for this. Oh, you've got diabetes. You need to go to the diabetes nurse for that'. (NHS 3)

4.3.5 Empowerment

Participants with lived experience

There was no standout evidence that participants felt empowered before diagnosis. Empowerment was a theme influenced by the four other principles. While not included in the trauma-informed principles, uncertainty before diagnosis appeared to overshadow participants' feelings of empowerment. Following a month of headaches, D2 YOD made an appointment with the GP. The GP wanted to investigate further. D2 YOD said:

'I'm never thinking dementia. I'm thinking, my god, brain tumour. You know, somethings no [not] right here. It's got to be a brain tumour'. Due to changes in behaviour D2 YOD would often think 'What's going on here, really, what is going on'. C1 expressed 'at 47 and 53 [years old] you don't think that these are symptoms of young onset dementia. I didn't even know what young onset dementia was, to be honest'. (C1)

Staff

Staff looked to empower individuals through knowledge and education. Ensuring that patients and their families are aware of the important aspects of their anticipatory care plans. NHS 2 says:

'have you already done Power of Attorney? Are you driving?' (NHS 2).

Often, patients are anxious about the future. NHS 2 found a general reluctance to care homes

'you mention care homes at the beginning and it's always never, never, never' (NHS 2).

NHS 3 states that their role is to provide them with a lot of practical advice and education, as well as information on how to manage the illness (NHS 3). When asked directly about empowering individuals affected by YOD, NHS 3 replied:

'Giving them sort of memory management tips, giving them some diaries, writing things down, using white boards, use of technology, all the kinda practical stuff. Actually get talking to them, talking to them through that, to see if it is something you would use? Would you have difficulty with that? Trying to assess as well, although I'm giving you this information, is it going to be useful to you?' (NHS 3)

Empowerment was viewed by a NHS staff member:

'About making them feel as independent as they can be, and making that clear, that's our goal as well. We want the same goals, so it's just checking in with them, but what's important to them? What goals do they want? And that's absolutely what we're looking towards, so that they are motivated to take in both energies or information and it's actually meaningful for them' (NHS 3),

Findings suggest education and person-centred care were pivotal for empowerment:

'Education is massive and making the connections with people like this is what's available. And that's where our clinical support worker really comes in. because she knows a lot of resources in the community, and she's got the time to really get to know them'. (NHS 3)

Additionally, focusing on patients' interests can support better engagement. NHS 3 gives an example:

'We had a patient that really liked [redacted]. She [the clinical support worker] went away and found lots of resources for them, contacted them, made sure they were suitable for them and provided the wife with the information' (NHS 3)

Maintaining empowerment was seen as difficult due to the progressive nature of YOD. When reflecting on the barriers of empowerment for carers, NHS 3 says:

'No matter what you give them, we can elevate a wee bit, but they're still stressed and they're still worried. They're still grieving for the future, and that doesn't really change'. (NHS 3)

The data collected reflected the experiences of the nine participants before, during, and after diagnosis on the YOD pathway, providing insight into how TIP can influence this pathway. This chapter represents the nine participants in the study throughout the

seven interviews conducted. The following chapter will examine the interpretations of the findings and their practical applications.

Chapter 5 Discussion

5.1 Summary of Key Findings

This appears to be the first study to explore how TIP can be applied to the diagnostic pathway of YOD in Scotland. Key findings will be presented in the context of existing literature around YOD, trauma and trauma-informed approaches to practice and care. Additionally, limitations, interpretations and recommendations will be discussed.

Findings from the study demonstrate the experiences of individuals with YOD, their caregivers, and health professionals regarding the application of trauma-informed principles in the YOD diagnostic pathway. There were several instances of a trauma-informed approach being needed, but it was not applied. This was notably at the pre-diagnostic stage, particularly in terms of safety. Collaboration and empowerment were impacted post-diagnosis due to the initial lack of safety. Changes to daily living from symptom onset caused stress for families. Throughout the findings, a thread of uncertainty emerged that had a detrimental impact on the participants' well-being. Although participants received a diagram in the PIS outlining the five trauma-informed principles, these principles were not directly discussed in any aspect of the interviews. However, this was attempted in the first interview, but it was clear this deductive approach would not work, as it confused the participant.

5.2 Interpretations

5.2.1 Safety

Establishing safety before a diagnosis was the key to developing the other trauma-informed principles throughout the diagnostic pathway. The findings indicated a clear sense of reduced emotional and physical safety from the initial conversation with health professionals to a final diagnosis. Establishing support services early, based on trusting relationships, is crucial at the onset of diagnosis (O'Malley et al., 2019; Ritchie et al., 2015). Inconsistencies in care, confusing language, and a lack of communication

were examples that participant stated reduced their safety. These are all elements which should be incorporated into support services for dementia to promote safety (Bergmann, Peper, and Bieber, 2022). The progression of YOD symptoms over time was linked to a lack of feeling physically safe. Carers and those with YOD were concerned about the future and how they would navigate support services through the progression of the diagnosis. For pre- and post-diagnosis care to be successfully integrated into families' lives, they must not be fragmented but provide a consistent avenue for impactful support (Smith et al., 2021; Novek and Menec, 2020).

Healthcare staff promoted safety by creating a transparent service with families. Staff recognised the stress of the pre-diagnosis stage and aimed to be upfront about a potential dementia diagnosis and provide resources for support. This included awareness of the unique challenges faced by families experiencing YOD, such as access to financial advice and support for young children. This demonstrates the need for implementation of SIGN 168 guidelines 2.1 'Identification and diagnosis of dementia,' by healthcare professionals (Health Improvement Scotland, 2023). There was evidence of re-traumatisation in the delivery of post-diagnosis support. Practitioners who have specific training and awareness of TIP can provide care that can minimise trauma (Dawson et al., 2021).

5.2.2 Trustworthiness

The initial feelings of insecurity and lack of safety became the shaky foundation of trust. Those with lived experience expressed a lack of confidence in health services. Participants often felt services were disjointed and not working together. Healthcare support is essential in maintaining trust by offering clarity and continuity (Anderson and Griffith, 2022). For the participants in this study, the pre-diagnosis stage took place during the COVID-19 pandemic. This may have created a heightened sense of distrust in public health, as well as increased waiting times and disruptions to the continuity of care offered (Leonard et al., 2021). Diagnostic assessments and services were often delivered remotely through phone calls, which may have contributed to health inequalities (Giebel et al., 2021).

Trusting relationships were frequently found with direct line managers where both YOD and carers felt supported by their workplace until they felt they had to leave. This

is encouraging, as a positive work environment after diagnosis can contribute to a sense of belonging and social inclusion (Silvaggi et al., 2020). Previous literature has found that when these elements of life are compromised, they can be linked to developing trauma (Berman, Montgomery and Ratner, 2020).

In establishing a trusting environment between patients and staff, it was clear that healthcare staff valued trust, interlaced with themes of choice and collaboration. Staff discussed providing PDS with options, such as allowing a friend or family member to attend meetings. There was also evidence that they connected trust with safety in approaching PDS calmly, providing continuity with the same practitioner and adapting to everyone's individual needs. This supports Gjellestad et al., (2022) findings, which describe trust as a careful balance with safety in dementia care delivered by healthcare professionals.

5.2.3 Choice

Having the ability to choose pre- and post-diagnosis stages of dementia is different from other life-limiting diseases, as decision-making capacity will decrease (Berlinger et al., 2024). There was a sense of awareness among the participants regarding this, and they wanted to be listened to at the pre-diagnosis stage. Participants were unsure of the support they needed and when they would require it. The sense of choice centred around what support to engage with, what clinicians were seen and having options for the future. Individuals with lived experience are best positioned to make informed decisions about their care (Bhatt et al., 2018). Participants were often confused about which services they needed, which was frequently due to the diagnostic delay. Referrals to different health services before a YOD diagnosis meant confusion when dementia was first mentioned. Long waiting times for appointments to mental health services can increase a YOD diagnosis by 6 months (Loi et al., 2021). With minimal pre-diagnosis support, participants felt lost regarding their future choices. This is a challenging time, often due to a lack of awareness and knowledge about YOD and the diagnosis process (Kårelind et al., 2024), which was evident in this study.

A valued element of PDS, staff discussed signposting patients to various services based on their needs. This came after the diagnosis, though, and did not take into consideration the time spent waiting for the pre-diagnosis. While signposting

interventions are necessary, there is a risk of needs being overlooked due to potentially long-term, complex care needs not being met and engagement with a service that lacks adequate support for their needs (Cantrell, Booth, and Chambers, 2024). Previous research tells us that long-term continuous support is what is needed in YOD pathway rather than short-term fixes (Mayrhofer et al., 2018).

5.2.4 Collaboration

YOD and carers presented an overall negative view of collaboration with support services, often seen as disjointed. Feelings ranged from frustration to being overwhelmed. Successful collaboration was viewed as a consistent service to rely on in the long term. Participants often felt disconnected or overwhelmed by the excessive amount of irrelevant information. This not only applies to those with a diagnosis but also to unpaid carers, where meaningful collaborations are often non-existent (Heintz et al., 2020). There was evidence of positive collaboration, which was attributed to regular meetings, consistency, and a well-suited support service. While collaboration may be difficult to measure, better communication between health boards and local organisations could lead to well-coordinated, sustainable support (Alderwick et al., 2021). A participant felt an over-the-phone assessment of their dementia was a 'mockery' as they used the internet to answer questions. Phone assessments for dementia may also overlook key components, such as observations on motor skills (Riley, McKinstry, and Fairhurst, 2022).

Stronger collaboration in the YOD diagnosis pathway could lead to a quicker diagnosis, earlier access to support services, and reduced stress (Loi et al., 2020). PDS staff would collaborate with other services to identify the most suitable support for patients. However, they raised awareness of poor collaboration between NHS health boards and social work. This was mainly due to funding and budget cuts, which are ongoing issues in the UK (Maynard, 2017). Fragmented collaboration of support services in the diagnostic pathway can increase caregiver burden as they have more responsibilities without the appropriate support (Laparidou et al., 2018). While literature suggests that carers and families are often isolated from PDS (Häikiö, Sagbakken, and Rugkåsa, 2020), the staff in this study did recognise the need to engage carers and families in their support model. Information exchange between health professionals, YOD, and carers should include management of stress,

development of coping skills, and education to facilitate a positive collaboration (Carter, Monaghan, and Santin, 2020).

5.2.5 Empowerment

The findings demonstrated a lack of empowerment throughout. It was clear that empowerment was influenced by the four other principles. To create a sense of empowerment in the YOD pathway, increased knowledge, impactful engagement with services, peer support, and a continuous support network must be present (Zhang et al., 2025). Post-diagnosis, empowerment can be seen in maintaining a sense of purpose in life such as through employment (Vliet et al., 2017). All participants with YOD in this study had to give up their employment, which had a detrimental impact on them. To achieve a sense of empowerment through employment, employers of individuals with YOD should support their development in competency, promote choice, and allow them to establish an 'occupational identity' (Andrew, Phillipson, and Sheridan, 2018). From pre-diagnosis, participants want to be involved in decision-making, continuity, peer support and having an active voice, which would enhance empowerment in the diagnostic pathway (McConnell et al., 2019).

The findings indicated that health staff made the connection with empowerment through the promotion of education, autonomy, and person-centred care. Staff presented the idea of giving patients tools to enhance their empowerment, but it is not always successful due to high levels of stress and distress.

5.2.6 Uncertainty

While 'uncertainty' is not a TI principle, the findings regarding uncertainty align with those of Meng et al. (2025), who also found the present and the future were significant challenges for participants. Both YOD and caregivers reported experiencing feelings of uncertainty before, during, and after diagnosis. While a YOD diagnosis was a relief and a gateway into accessing formal PDS, the lack of support and guidance from symptom onset caused notable stress and anxiety (Sideman et al., 2022). Like the findings by Campbell et al. (2016), this study found that uncertainty was a key feature running through the diagnostic pathway, which may also be linked to broader mental health challenges, such as anxiety, where uncertainty plays a central role (Andrews et al., 2023).

5.2.7 Daily living

While not part of the trauma-informed principles, there was a clear subtheme of participants' low resilience with the daily struggles of a progressive disease. This was evident in all stages of the diagnostic pathway. There was a sense that the stress and anxiety of coping day-to-day negatively impacted the experience of those currently dealing with YOD (Johannessen et al., 2018). The onset of YOD symptoms at such a young age, changes in daily routine and the feeling of losing themselves were significant stressors. Losing their future, for both YOD and carers, presented emotional turmoil for participants, where this finding aligned with Rabanal et al., 2018 and Busted, Nielsen, and Birkelund (2020), who also highlighted the importance of having a purpose both now and in the future. All participants with lived experience mentioned the importance of peer support. Participants felt that having someone in a similar circumstance to offer advice on day-to-day living with young-onset dementia would be valuable. This aligns with the findings of Sullivan et al. (2022), who highlighted the importance of having tailored peer support models specifically for YOD and their caregivers. Although YOD and carers viewed peer support as a positive aspect, staff in the study reported there is often a reluctance among patients to engage with peer support offered to them. This may be due to the delivery method provided, where a flexible approach can lead to increased engagement, including both virtual meetings and face-to-face interactions (Carter, Monaghan, and Santin, 2020). Previous research offered advice on peer activities that would extend independence for longer, such as food shopping (Mayrhofer et al., 2018).

The figure below outlines key safety and communication challenges across four stages of the diagnostic process - Before, During, After, and Trauma-Informed. It highlights how uncertainty, lack of continuity, and inconsistent support services undermine psychological and physical safety, collaboration, and trust. The trauma-informed section emphasises the difficulty of applying trauma-informed principles when safety is compromised early in the process.

Figure 3. A diagram representing findings

5.3 Limitations

There are limitations to this study. It consisted of a small sample of nine participants (three YOD, three carers, and three staff). However, this was appropriate for the study's timeframe. Diversity was limited in terms of ethnicity. Some participants noted that the language used in the study's title was confusing. They were not sure what was meant by the word 'trauma'. This may have deterred other participants from volunteering. To combat this, the researcher distributed a recruitment video to clarify and simplify the study's explanation. Although this was a small project, full NHS ethical

review and approval were needed. This process altered the study's trajectory by several months.

5.4 Implications

The diagnostic experiences of people with young-onset dementia and their families in this study showed a gap in applying trauma-informed principles to the YOD pathway. Participants with lived experience emphasised the importance of establishing safety before diagnosis. Consequently, the absence of safety affected all other trauma-informed principles. Without this initial trauma-informed principle being met, it was clear other principles would be impacted before, during and after diagnosis. Pre-diagnosis is a crucial time to introduce support services (O'Malley et al., 2019). Previous research highlights that a prolonged diagnostic pathway can further increase the risk of trauma or re-traumatisation (Loi et al., 2020; Chiari et al., 2022). A trauma-informed approach to care may reduce the risk of re-traumatisation and minimise stress and distress (Muskett, 2014; Cations et al., 2021). A connection built on safety from the outset can increase the likelihood of continuity of support, reduce stress, and lead to positive engagement with service users and health care professionals (Novek and Menec, 2020). To reduce emotional stress, support services and signposting should begin as early as possible (Stamou et al., 2021).

The study emphasised the importance of incorporating daily living into the pathway and its potential to have a profound impact on individuals. Managing cognitive changes in day-to-day living with a lack of understanding of YOD can lead to a sense of loss and questioning of one's identity (Johannessen et al., 2018). The disruption of everyday life cannot be ignored and can develop trauma (Berman, Montgomery, and Ratner, 2020).

Health professional staff who were interviewed were passionate about YOD and delivering person-centred care. The implementation of trauma-informed principles was evident at the post-diagnosis stage. However, this is limited to one year with the option to contact the team for additional support in the future. Key aspects of participant interviews related to the Alzheimer Scotland (2025) campaign for change –

- better access to diagnosis
- expanded post-diagnostic support

- increased support for carers
- a fair and equitable social care system

Alzheimer Scotland’s 5 Pillars Model of Post-Diagnostic Support, as shown in Figure 3 below, incorporates trauma-informed principles in various aspects of this approach. This model could also be applied pre-diagnosis, not only by NHS staff but also by services used for signposting referrals. Feedback has shown this model works well post-diagnosis (Scottish Government, 2017). Adopting this model pre-diagnosis would enhance trauma-informed approaches as early as possible.

Figure 4: Alzheimer Scotland’s 5 Pillar Model of Post-Diagnostic Support

A progressive, life-altering diagnosis of dementia can reduce an individual’s ability to feel empowered (Geugten and Goossensen, 2019). It can also increase the likelihood of trauma and re-traumatisation (Ganzel, 2018). However, research on other

progressive diseases, such as Parkinson's, can benefit from a trauma-informed approach to minimise the risk of re-traumatisation (Ricks-Aherne, Wallace and Kusmaul, 2020). Adopting a trauma-informed approach for those facing adversity in the YOD diagnostic pathway could have a similar impact (Jackson, Maurin, and Fedio, 2024; Li et al., 2020).

Previous research has suggested that the onset of YOD can lead to poorer mental and physical health (Magruder, McLaughlin and Elmore Borbon, 2017). A nationwide implementation of the five trauma-informed principles in public health diagnostic pathways in the UK could again minimise the risk of trauma and re-traumatisation Emsley et al. (2022). Despite this, there is no explicit literature on TIC and the YOD diagnostic pathway. Further research on this topic will be critical in improving the YOD diagnostic pathway.

5.5 Conclusion

Considering the young-onset dementia diagnostic pathway, health professionals should adopt a trauma-informed approach when working with those with YOD and their families. The potentially negative impact of YOD pre- and post-diagnosis could lead to trauma or re-traumatisation; therefore, implementing the five NES TIP: 1. Safety, 2. trustworthiness, 3. Choice, 4. Collaboration, 5. Empowerment within the YOD pathway can address this risk and provide tailored support to minimise it. As the prevalence of YOD increases, it is crucial to ensure that age-appropriate support needs are met through continuity of services. A YOD diagnostic pathway which increases feelings of safety from the pre-diagnosis stage will enhance positive feelings of trust, choice, collaboration, and empowerment. Health professionals should acknowledge the unique challenges and daily stressors of everyday life faced by those under the age of 65 years with dementia and their families to reduce emotional stress. The pathway should have transparency across all stages to minimise the feelings of uncertainty among families. Further research on this topic will support health inequalities faced by those with YOD and their carers and families.

5.6 Recommendations

Practice Recommendations

These focus on improving service delivery and professional development:

- Establish pre-diagnosis support pathways for individuals with Young Onset Dementia (YOD) and their families to foster safety, trust, and emotional preparedness before formal diagnosis.
- Integrate peer support roles into dementia services, ensuring individuals with lived experience can offer practical, holistic guidance on navigating daily life post-diagnosis.
- Embed trauma-informed training into the professional development of healthcare staff involved in the YOD diagnostic pathway, enhancing empathy, communication, and patient-centred care.
- Develop trauma-sensitive protocols for initial assessments and diagnostic conversations to reduce distress and improve engagement.

Research Recommendations

These aim to explore, evaluate, and expand understanding of the issues raised:

- Conduct a feasibility study on implementing pre-diagnosis support models in clinical settings, assessing impact on patient and family outcomes.
- Explore the role and impact of peer support in YOD care through qualitative case studies or participatory research methods.
- Evaluate the effectiveness of trauma-informed training for healthcare professionals in dementia services, measuring changes in practice and patient experience.
- Investigate barriers to ethical approval for small-scale studies involving lone researchers, particularly in contexts involving vulnerable populations, to inform streamlined processes.
- Pilot a condensed NHS ethics application model tailored for low-risk, time-limited research projects, with a focus on inclusivity and accessibility.

Policy Recommendations

These support systemic change and long-term sustainability:

- Advocate for policy changes that recognise the importance of pre-diagnosis support in dementia care pathways, especially for YOD.
- Recommend formal inclusion of peer support roles in dementia service frameworks, supported by funding and training.
- Propose revisions to NHS ethics review processes for small-scale, lone-researcher studies to reduce administrative burden and promote equity in research access.
- Encourage national adoption of trauma-informed principles across dementia care services, supported by policy guidance and professional standards.

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Appendices 1 – 7

Appendix 1 – CASP Qualitative tool

Critical Appraisal
Skills Programme

CASP Checklist:

For Qualitative Research

Reviewer Name:	
Paper Title:	
Author:	
Web Link:	
Appraisal Date:	

During critical appraisal, never make assumptions about what the researchers have done. If it is not possible to tell, use the “Can’t tell” response box. If you can’t tell, at best it means the researchers have not been explicit or transparent, but at worst it could mean the researchers have not undertaken a particular task or process. Once you’ve finished the critical appraisal, if there are a large number of “Can’t tell” responses, consider whether the findings of the study are trustworthy and interpret the results with caution.

Section A Are the results valid?	
<p>1. Was there a clear statement of the aims of the research?</p>	<p>Yes No Can't Tell</p>
<p><i>CONSIDER:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>what was the goal of the research?</i> • <i>why was it thought important?</i> • <i>its relevance</i> 	
<p>2. Is a qualitative methodology appropriate?</p>	<p>Yes No Can't Tell</p>

<p><i>CONSIDER:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>If the research seeks to interpret or illuminate the actions and/or subjective experiences of research participants</i> <i>Is qualitative research the right methodology for addressing the research goal?</i> 	
<p>3. Was the research design appropriate to address the aims of the research?</p>	<p>Yes No Can't Tell</p>
<p><i>CONSIDER:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>if the researcher has justified the research design (e.g., have they discussed how they decided which method to use)</i> 	
<p>4. Was the recruitment strategy appropriate to the aims of the research?</p>	<p>Yes No Can't Tell</p>
<p><i>CONSIDER:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>If the researcher has explained how the participants were selected</i> <i>If they explained why the participants they selected were the most appropriate to provide access to the type of knowledge sought by the study</i> 	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>If there are any discussions around recruitment (e.g. why some people chose not to take part)</i> 	
<p>5. Was the data collected in a way that addressed the research issue?</p>	<p>Yes No Can't Tell</p>
<p>CONSIDER:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>If the setting for the data collection was justified</i> <i>If it is clear how data were collected (e.g. focus group, semi-structured interview etc.)</i> <i>If the researcher has justified the methods chosen</i> <i>If the researcher has made the methods explicit (e.g. for interview method, is there an indication of how interviews are conducted, or did they use a topic guide)</i> <i>If methods were modified during the study. If so, has the researcher explained how and why</i> <i>If the form of data is clear (e.g. tape recordings, video material, notes etc.)</i> <i>If the researcher has discussed saturation of data</i> 	
<p>6. Has the relationship between researcher and participants been adequately considered?</p>	<p>Yes No Can't Tell</p>
<p>CONSIDER:</p>	

- *If the researcher critically examined their own role, potential bias and influence during (a) formulation of the research questions (b) data collection, including sample recruitment and choice of location*
- *How the researcher responded to events during the study and whether they considered the implications of any changes in the research design*

Section B: What are the results?

7. Have ethical issues been taken into consideration?	Yes No Can't Tell
---	-------------------

- CONSIDER:**
- *If there are sufficient details of how the research was explained to participants for the reader to assess whether ethical standards were maintained*
 - *If the researcher has discussed issues raised by the study (e.g. issues around informed consent or confidentiality or how they have handled the effects of the study on the participants during and after the study)*
 - *If approval has been sought from the ethics committee*

8. Was the data analysis sufficiently rigorous?	Yes No Can't Tell
---	-------------------

- CONSIDER:**
- *If there is an in-depth description of the analysis process*

- *If thematic analysis is used. If so, is it clear how the categories/themes were derived from the data*
- *Whether the researcher explains how the data presented were selected from the original sample to demonstrate the analysis process*
- *If sufficient data are presented to support the findings*
- *To what extent contradictory data are taken into account*
- *Whether the researcher critically examined their own role, potential bias and influence during analysis and selection of data for presentation*

9. Is there a clear statement of findings?	Yes No Can't Tell
--	-------------------

- CONSIDER:**
- *If the findings are explicit*
 - *If there is adequate discussion of the evidence both for and against the researcher's arguments*
 - *If the researcher has discussed the credibility of their findings (e.g. triangulation, respondent validation, more than one analyst)*
 - *If the findings are discussed in relation to the original research question*

Section C: Will the results help locally?

10. How valuable is the research?	Yes No Can't Tell
-----------------------------------	-------------------

- CONSIDER:**

- *If the researcher discusses the contribution the study makes to existing knowledge or understanding (e.g., do they consider the findings in relation to current practice or policy, or relevant research-based literature*
- *If they identify new areas where research is necessary*
- *If the researchers have discussed whether or how the findings can be transferred to other populations or considered other ways the research may be used*

APPRAISAL SUMMARY: *List key points from your critical appraisal that need to be considered when assessing the validity of the results and their usefulness in decision-making.*

Positive/Methodologically sound	Negative/Relatively poor methodology	Unknowns

Referencing recommendation:

CASP recommends using the Harvard style referencing, which is an author/date method. Sources are cited within the body of your assignment by giving the name of the author(s) followed by the date of publication. All other details about the publication are given in the list of references or bibliography at the end.

Example:

Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (2024). CASP (insert name of checklist i.e. systematic reviews with meta-analysis of randomised controlled trials (RCTs) Checklist.) [online] Available at: insert URL. Accessed: insert date accessed.

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Appendix 2 – Excel Literature Review Example

	Section A - 1. Was there a clear statement of the aims of the research?	Section A - 2. Is a qualitative methodology appropriate?	Is it worth continuing?	Section A - 3. Was the research design appropriate to address the aims of the research?	Section A - 4. Was the recruitment strategy appropriate to the aims of the study?	Section A - 5. Was the data collected in a way that addressed the research issue?	Section A - 6. Has the relationship between researcher and participant been adequately considered?	Section B - 7. Have ethical issues been taken into consideration?	Section B - 8. Was the data analysis sufficiently rigorous?	Section B - 9. Is there a clear statement of findings?	Section C - 10. How valuable is the research?	Relevance Score	Notes
Paper for Appraisal													
Gerritsen, A.A.J., Bakker, C., Verhey, F.R.J., Pijnenburg, Y.A.L., Millenaar, J.K., de Vugt, M.E. and Koopmans, R.T.C.M. (2019). Survival and life-expectancy in a young-onset dementia cohort with six years of follow-up: the Need/D-study. <i>International Psychogeriatrics</i> , [online] 31(12), pp.1781-1789. doi: 10.1017/S10416160219000152.	Yes	Yes - longitudinal 2-year Dutch study / mixed-methods	Yes	Yes - 198 participants, male and female, with a mean age of 60.9 years old, investigating the decline of cognitive function in individuals with a diagnosis of YOD	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Highlights the rapid decline in those with YOD, suggesting the gap in knowledge when addressing the unmet needs of those with a diagnosis of YOD potentially due to prolonged time to diagnosis	High	Gerritsen et al., (2019) concluded the mean of YOD in the 198 participants was 209 m with 38.9% of the participants dying - Not

Appendix 3 – Literature Review Table

Author (s)	Year	Study Title
Gerritsen et al	2018	Survival and life-expectancy in a young-onset dementia cohort with six years of follow-up
Rabanal et al	2018	Understanding the needs and experiences of people with young onset dementia: a qualitative study
Johannessen et al	2018	'To be, or not to be': experiencing deterioration among people with young-onset dementia living alone
Clemerson, Walsh and Isaac	2013	Towards living well with young onset dementia: An exploration of coping from the perspective of those diagnosed
Loi et al	2022	Factors associated with diagnostic delay in younger-onset dementia diagnostic delay in younger-onset dementia.
Busted, Nielson and Birkelund	2020	'Sometimes it feels like thinking in syrup' – the experience of losing sense of self in those with young onset dementia
Novak and Menec	2020	Age, Dementia, and Diagnostic Candidacy:

		Examining the Diagnosis of Young Onset Dementia Using the Candidacy Framework
Mayrhofer et al	2018	Young onset dementia: Public involvement in co-designing community-based support
Oyebode et al	2023	Establishing and sustaining high-quality services for people with young onset dementia: the perspective of senior service providers and commissioners.
Craftsman et al	2019	Caring for older people with dementia reliving past trauma.
van Vliet et al	2017	Feeling useful and engaged in daily life: exploring the experiences of people with young-onset dementia.
Emsley et al	2022	Trauma-informed Care in the UK: Where Are we? a Qualitative Study of Health Policies and Professional Perspectives
Gori et al	2021	Pathways to post-traumatic growth in cancer patients: moderated mediation and single mediation analyses with

		resilience, personality, and coping strategies
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Appendix 4 – Participant Information Pack YOD

Participant Pack

Project Title: 'Trauma and dementia diagnosis: An investigation of the potential for a trauma-informed pathway through the diagnosis of dementia, for people under 65 years old'.

Ethics Approval Number: 340377

Supervisors: Dr Anna Jack-Waugh and Dr Eileen Harkess-Murphy

Lead Student Researcher: Kelly Kelly

Email: [REDACTED]

X: @kellykresearch

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Participant Information Sheet

Project Title: 'Trauma and dementia diagnosis: An investigation of the potential for a trauma-informed pathway through the diagnosis of dementia, for people under 65 years old'.

Ethics Approval Number: 340377

Supervisors: Dr Anna Jack-Waugh and Dr Eileen Harkess-Murphy

Lead Student Researcher: Kelly Kelly **Email:** [REDACTED]

The researcher

I have experience working with people with dementia and I am passionate about understanding the needs and wishes of people living with dementia and their caregivers. I am a registered mental health nurse specialising in dementia care and have a master's degree and an honours degree in Psychology.

Aims of the project

I am looking to understand your personal experience from noticing changes to receiving a diagnosis of dementia. I will explore how trauma-informed principles can improve an individual's dementia diagnosis for people with young-onset dementia.

What is a trauma-informed pathway?

Trauma is an event or series of events that is emotionally or physically harmful to someone. These events can be stressful and scary, happen at any age and can be difficult to cope with for life. A trauma-informed pathway is when health professionals, such as nurses, doctors, physiotherapists, aim to understand someone's trauma and how they can support someone to feel safe, free to choose, and listening to what someone needs and wants. This is unique to the person.

Why am I being invited to take part?

Participants with a diagnosis of dementia who received their diagnosis under the age of 65 years old and family/carer of those with a diagnosis are being asked to take part in interviews with myself to explore their dementia diagnosis journey.

What will I be asked to do?

If you decide to take part and complete of a consent form, you will be asked to attend an interview with myself in a location of your choice (this could be your home, Alzheimer Scotland premises, UWS campus, Microsoft Teams etc) and you are able to bring a family member or carer to support you if you wish to do so. It is important to me you feel comfortable and can speak freely. Your contribution is greatly valued and I am privileged to be part of this.

How much time will the project take?

Interviews are expected to last one hour. I expect the project will be completed for October 2024 where you will be updated throughout this time with reports and findings.

What happens to the information in the project?

Interviews will be recorded using an audio recorder and converted into written format, where you will remain anonymous throughout the project. Presentation of data will include a report, presentations delivered in-person and via Microsoft Teams, poster presentation, attending relevant conferences, and meeting groups with all participants receiving feedback on findings. All findings will be stored on a laptop at The University of the West of Scotland Campus. All data will be kept in line with UWS secure systems - this will be password protected and stored securely.

Do I need to take part?

No, you do not have to take part. As participation in this study is voluntary, you are not under any obligation to be involved.

What if I change my mind and do not want to continue with the study?

If you do decide to take part, you can withdraw at any time without providing a reason. If you feel distressed throughout the project, you can withdraw at any time and will be supported. The project team can signpost you in accessing further support. Wendy

Rankin-Smith (Active Voice Lead) and Jane Mimnaugh (Alzheimer Scotland Dementia Nurse Consultant and Old Age Psychiatry) can be contacted after the interview and offer ongoing support.

There will be no financial incentive and participation is voluntary. All participants have the right to refuse to take part in the study or withdraw at any time, without providing a reason.

Prompt Sheet

Thank you for deciding to take part in this research. Your contribution to this project is invaluable and I am grateful to you for sharing your experience with me.

The interview will cover the following topics –

- Pre-diagnosis - What did you notice in those early days before your diagnosis?
- Diagnosis Experience – What can you tell me about your diagnosis journey?
- Post-diagnosis – What has life been like since your diagnosis?

I will ask you to reflect on a time throughout your journey where you felt –

1. Safe.
2. Trusting.
3. Had a clear choice.
4. Collaborated – health professionals, family/carers etc.
5. Felt empowered

This will help me to understand if trauma-informed principles played a part in your experience and if they did play a part, in what way.

What is a trauma-informed pathway?

Trauma is an event or series of events that is emotionally or physically harmful to someone. These events can be stressful and scary, happen at any age and can be difficult to cope with for life. A trauma-informed pathway is when health professionals, such as nurses, doctors, physiotherapists, aim to understand someone's trauma and how they can support someone to feel safe, free to choose, and listening to what someone needs and wants. This is unique to the person.

TRAUMA-INFORMED PRINCIPLES: What does this mean?

Data Protection Information Sheet

What personal data will be used?

Participant's age, gender and preferred contact method will be taken where each participant will be allocated a code to ensure anonymity throughout transcriptions and direct quotes such as P1, P2, P3... etc. The codes will be used when quoting and referencing participants and participant codes will be stored separately from the anonymised interview transcripts.

How will my data be stored?

Data collection will be encrypted with myself and two project supervisors having access to this. I will use a secure platform to transcribe audio recordings. I will comply with all UWS Data Protection regulations, Research Data Management and NHS Code of Confidentiality. Storage of data will be held on UWS secure systems, and this will be password protected in line with UWS Protocol for the Use of Cloud Storage. When transcribing the data, I will be in a secure environment at UWS campus with no interruptions and using headphones when listening to audio recordings.

After the project has been completed?

All data recorded in all formats will be uploaded to the UWS research repository system in line with the UWS Research Data Management Procedure.

Who can I contact if I have a complaint?

If you want to complain about how researchers have handled your information, you should contact the research team. If you are not happy after that, you can contact the UWS Data Protection Officer. The research team can give you details of the right Data Protection Officer.

Will the use of my data meet GDPR rules?

GDPR stands for the General Data Protection Regulation. In the UK we follow the GDPR rules and have a law called the Data Protection Act. All research using patient data must follow UK laws and rules. Universities, NHS organisations and companies may use patient data to do research to make health and care better.

When companies do research to develop new treatments, they need to be able to prove that they need to use patient data for the research, and that they need to do the research to develop new treatments. In legal terms this means that they have a 'legitimate interest' in using patient data.

Universities and the NHS are funded from taxes and they are expected to do research as part of their job. They still need to be able to prove that they need to use patient data for the research. In legal terms this means that they use patient data as part of 'a task in the public interest'.

If they could do the research without using patient data they would not be allowed to get your data.

Researchers must show that their research takes account of the views of patients and ordinary members of the public. They must also show how they protect the privacy of the people who take part. An NHS research ethics committee checks this before the research starts.

All participants have the right to refuse to take part in the study or withdraw at any time, without providing a reason.

Consent Form

Project Title: 'Trauma and dementia diagnosis: An investigation of the potential for a trauma-informed pathway through the diagnosis of dementia, for people under 65 years old'.

Ethics Approval Number: 34077

Supervisors: Dr Anna Jack-Waugh and Dr Eileen Harkess-Murphy

Lead Student Researcher: Kelly Kelly

Email: [REDACTED]

Statement	Yes / No	Signature and Date
I confirm I have read and understood the participant information sheet provided and have had the opportunity to ask questions.	Yes / No	
I understand the project is voluntary with no financial incentive and I am free to withdraw at any time without providing a reason.	Yes / No	
I understand findings from the project will be reported anonymously protecting my identity and all information will be stored securely.	Yes / No	
I understand the project involves interviews that will be audibly recorded.	Yes / No	
I understand if I choose my interview to take place over Microsoft Teams it will be recorded.	Yes / No	
I agree to quotes from the interview being used anonymously.	Yes / No	
I understand findings will be discussed with the researcher and lead supervisors.	Yes / No	
I understand I am free to contact the researcher at any time throughout the project to ask questions.	Yes / No	

I agree to the researcher taking written notes throughout conversations.	Yes / No	
I agree to take part in this research.	Yes / No	

Consent form to be completed and returned to Kelly Kelly at

[REDACTED]

Appendix 5 – Participant information pack Carer

Participant Pack

Project Title: 'Trauma and dementia diagnosis: An investigation of the potential for a trauma-informed pathway through the diagnosis of dementia, for people under 65 years old'.

Ethics Approval Number: 340377

Supervisors: Dr Anna Jack-Waugh and Dr Eileen Harkess-Murphy

Lead Student Researcher: Kelly Kelly

Email: [REDACTED]

X: @kellykresearch

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Ethics Approval Number: 340377

Supervisors: Dr Anna Jack-Waugh and Dr Eileen Harkess-Murphy

Lead Student Researcher: Kelly Kelly **Email:** [REDACTED]

The researcher

I have experience working with people with dementia and I am passionate about understanding the needs and wishes of people living with dementia and their caregivers. I am a registered mental health nurse specialising in dementia care and have a master's degree and an honours degree in Psychology.

Aims of the project

I am looking to understand your personal experience from noticing changes in your family member or those you care for, to them receiving a diagnosis of dementia. I will explore how trauma-informed principles can improve an individual's dementia diagnosis for people with young-onset dementia and their family and carers.

What is a trauma-informed pathway?

Trauma is an event or series of events that is emotionally or physically harmful to someone. These events can be stressful and scary, happen at any age and can be difficult to cope with for life. A trauma-informed pathway is when health professionals, such as nurses, doctors, physiotherapists, aim to understand someone's trauma and how they can support someone to feel safe, free to choose, and listening to what someone needs and wants. This is unique to the person.

Why am I being invited to take part?

Family and carers of those with a diagnosis of dementia under the age of 65 years old are being asked to take part in interviews with the participant with a dementia diagnosis

and myself to explore the dementia diagnosis journey. Those participants with a diagnosis of dementia will decide if they would like their family member or carer to be present in the interview.

What will I be asked to do?

If the participant with a dementia diagnosis who you are a family member of or their carer chose to have you present in the interview, and you decide to take part and complete of a consent form, you will be asked to attend an interview with the participant with a dementia diagnosis who you are a family member of or their carer with myself in a location of your choice (this could be your home, Alzheimer Scotland premises, UWS campus, Microsoft Teams etc). It is important to me you feel comfortable and can speak freely. Your contribution is greatly valued, and I am privileged to be part of this.

How much time will the project take?

Interviews are expected to last one hour. I expect the project will be completed for October 2024 where you will be updated throughout this time with reports and findings.

What happens to the information in the project?

Interviews will be recorded using an audio recorder and converted into written format, where you will remain anonymous throughout the project. Presentation of data will include a report, presentations delivered in-person and via Microsoft Teams, poster presentation, attending relevant conferences, and meeting groups with all participants receiving feedback on findings. All findings will be stored on a laptop at The University of the West of Scotland Campus. All data will be kept in line with UWS secure systems - this will be password protected and stored securely.

Do I need to take part?

No, you do not have to take part. As participation in this study is voluntary, you are not under any obligation to be involved.

What if I change my mind and do not want to continue with the study?

If you do decide to take part and later wish to withdraw without providing a reason or feel any distress throughout the project, you can withdraw at any time where any audio recordings will be erased. The project team can signpost you in accessing further support. Wendy Rankin-Smith (Active Voice Lead) and Jane Mimnaugh (Alzheimer Scotland Dementia Nurse Consultant and Old Age Psychiatry) can be contacted after the interview and offer ongoing support.

There will be no financial incentive and participation is voluntary. All participants have the right to refuse to take part in the study or withdraw at any time, without providing a reason.

Prompt Sheet

Thank you for deciding to take part in this research. Your contribution to this project is invaluable and I am grateful to you for sharing your experience with me.

The interview will cover the following topics –

- Pre-diagnosis - What did you notice in those early days before diagnosis?
- Diagnosis Experience – What can you tell me about your experience in the diagnosis journey?
- Post-diagnosis – What has life been like since the diagnosis?

I will ask you to reflect on a time throughout your journey where you felt –

1. Safe.
2. Trusting.
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5. Felt empowered

This will help me to understand if trauma-informed principles played a part in your experience and if they did play a part, in what way.

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Trauma is an event or series of events that is emotionally or physically harmful to someone. These events can be stressful and scary, happen at any age and can be difficult to cope with for life. A trauma-informed pathway is when health professionals, such as nurses, doctors, physiotherapists, aim to understand someone's trauma and how they can support someone to feel safe, free to choose, and listening to what someone needs and wants. This is unique to the person.

TRAUMA-INFORMED PRINCIPLES: What does this mean?

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What personal data will be used?

Participant's age, gender and preferred contact method will be taken where each participant will be allocated a code to ensure anonymity throughout transcriptions and direct quotes such as P1, P2, P3... etc. The codes will be used when quoting and referencing participants and participant codes will be stored separately from the anonymised interview transcripts.

How will my data be stored?

Data collection will be encrypted with myself and two project supervisors having access to this. I will use a secure platform to transcribe audio recordings. I will comply with all UWS Data Protection regulations, Research Data Management and NHS Code of Confidentiality. Storage of data will be held on UWS secure systems, and this will be password protected in line with UWS Protocol for the Use of Cloud Storage. When transcribing the data, I will be in a secure environment at UWS campus with no interruptions and using headphones when listening to audio recordings.

After the project has been completed?

All data recorded in all formats will be uploaded to the UWS research repository system in line with the UWS Research Data Management Procedure.

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If you want to complain about how researchers have handled your information, you should contact the research team. If you are not happy after that, you can contact the UWS Data Protection Officer. The research team can give you details of the right Data Protection Officer.

Will the use of my data meet GDPR rules?

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When companies do research to develop new treatments, they need to be able to prove that they need to use patient data for the research, and that they need to do the research to develop new treatments. In legal terms this means that they have a 'legitimate interest' in using patient data.

Universities and the NHS are funded from taxes and they are expected to do research as part of their job. They still need to be able to prove that they need to use patient data for the research. In legal terms this means that they use patient data as part of 'a task in the public interest'.

If they could do the research without using patient data they would not be allowed to get your data.

Researchers must show that their research takes account of the views of patients and ordinary members of the public. They must also show how they protect the privacy of the people who take part. An NHS research ethics committee checks this before the research starts.

All participants have the right to refuse to take part in the study or withdraw at any time, without providing a reason.

Consent Form

Project Title: 'Trauma and dementia diagnosis: An investigation of the potential for a trauma-informed pathway through the diagnosis of dementia, for people under 65 years old'.

Ethics Approval Number: 34077

Supervisors: Dr Anna Jack-Waugh and Dr Eileen Harkess-Murphy

Lead Student Researcher: Kelly Kelly

Email: [REDACTED]

Statement	Yes / No	Signature and Date
I confirm I have read and understood the participant information sheet provided and have had the opportunity to ask questions.	Yes / No	
I understand the project is voluntary with no financial incentive and I am free to withdraw at any time without providing a reason.	Yes / No	
I understand findings from the project will be reported anonymously protecting my identity and all information will be stored securely.	Yes / No	
I understand the project involves interviews that will be audibly recorded.	Yes / No	
I understand if I choose my interview to take place over Microsoft Teams it will be recorded.	Yes / No	
I agree to quotes from the interview being used anonymously.	Yes / No	
I understand findings will be discussed with the researcher and lead supervisors.	Yes / No	
I understand I am free to contact the researcher at any time throughout the project to ask questions.	Yes / No	

I agree to the researcher taking written notes throughout conversations.	Yes / No	
I agree to take part in this research.	Yes / No	

Consent form to be completed and returned to Kelly Kelly at B00407591@studentmail.uws.ac.uk

Appendix 6 – Participant information pack NHS

Participant Pack

Project Title: 'Trauma and dementia diagnosis: An investigation of the potential for a trauma-informed pathway through the diagnosis of dementia, for people under 65 years old'.

Ethics Approval Number: 340377

Supervisors: Dr Anna Jack-Waugh and Dr Eileen Harkess-Murphy

Lead Student Researcher: Kelly Kelly

Email: [REDACTED]

X: @kellykresearch

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Participant Information Sheet

NHS Staff

Project Title: 'Trauma and dementia diagnosis: An investigation of the potential for a trauma-informed pathway through the diagnosis of dementia, for people under 65 years old'.

Ethics Approval Number: 340377

Supervisors: Dr Anna Jack-Waugh and Dr Eileen Harkess-Murphy

Lead Student Researcher: Kelly Kelly **Email:** [REDACTED]

The researcher

I have experience working with people with dementia and I am passionate about enhancing the quality of life for individuals with dementia and their caregivers. I am a registered mental health nurse specialising in dementia care and have a master's degree and an honours degree in Psychology.

Aims of the project

This project aims to investigate the potential for a trauma-informed pathway through the diagnosis of dementia, for people under 65 years of age. The study sets out to understand the diagnostic experiences of people with young onset dementia and their families, and health professionals involved in the diagnosis of dementia. The research will explore how trauma-informed principles are applied in the diagnostic experience and the potential of how a trauma-informed framework can improve the diagnostic experience for people with young-onset dementia.

What is a trauma-informed pathway?

Trauma is an event or series of events that is emotionally or physically harmful to someone. These events can be stressful and scary, happen at any age and can be difficult to cope with for life. A trauma-informed pathway is when health professionals, such as nurses, doctors, physiotherapists, aim to understand someone's trauma and how they can support someone to feel safe, free to choose, and listening to what someone needs and wants. This is unique to the person.

Why am I being invited to take part?

Participants from NHS Lanarkshire health board who are part of the diagnostic dementia journey of people under 65 years old, are being asked to take part in interviews with myself to explore the diagnostic experience of an individual living with dementia.

What will I be asked to do?

If you decide to take part and complete of a consent form, you will be asked to attend an interview with myself in a location of your choice (this could be your workplace, UWS campus, Microsoft Teams etc). It is important to me you feel comfortable and can speak freely. Your contribution is greatly appreciated and I am privileged to be part of this.

How much time will the project take?

Interviews are expected to last one hour. I expect the project will be completed for October 2024 where you will be updated throughout this time with reports and findings.

What happens to the information in the project?

Interviews will be recorded using an audio recorder and converted into written format, where you will remain anonymous throughout the project. Presentation of data will include a report, presentations delivered in-person and via Microsoft Teams, poster presentation, attending relevant conferences, and meeting groups with all participants receiving feedback on findings. All findings will be stored on a laptop at The University of the West of Scotland Campus. All data will be kept in line with UWS secure systems - this will be password protected and stored securely.

Do I need to take part?

No, you do not have to take part. As participation in this study is voluntary, you are not under any obligation to be involved.

What if I change my mind and do not want to continue with the study?

If you do decide to take part, you can withdraw at any time without providing a reason. If you feel distressed throughout the project, you can withdraw at any time and will be

supported. The project team can signpost you in accessing further support. Wendy Rankin-Smith (Active Voice Lead). Jane Mimnaugh (Alzheimer Scotland Dementia Nurse Consultant and Old Age Psychiatry) will be available to meet with NHS staff individually for a debriefing should the staff require additional support and reflection.

There will be no financial incentive and participation is voluntary. All participants have the right to refuse to take part in the study or withdraw at any time, without providing a reason.

Prompt Sheet

Thank you for deciding to take part in this research. Your contribution to this project is invaluable and I am grateful to you for sharing your experience with me.

The interview will cover the following topics –

- Pre-diagnosis
- Diagnosis Experience
- Post-diagnosis

I will ask you to reflect on a time throughout your career where you have supported an individual with a diagnosis of young onset dementia to feel –

1. Safe.
2. Trusting.
3. Had a clear choice.
4. Collaborated – health professionals, family/carers etc.
5. Felt empowered.

This will help me to understand if trauma-informed principles played a part in your experience as a health professional and if they did play a part, in what way.

What is a trauma-informed pathway?

Trauma is an event or series of events that is emotionally or physically harmful to someone. These events can be stressful and scary, happen at any age and can be difficult to cope with for life. A trauma-informed pathway is when health professionals, such as nurses, doctors, physiotherapists, aim to understand someone's trauma and how they can support someone to feel safe, free to choose, and listening to what someone needs and wants. This is unique to the person.

TRAUMA-INFORMED PRINCIPLES: What does this mean?

Data Protection Information Sheet

What personal data will be used?

Participant's age, gender and preferred contact method will be taken where each participant will be allocated a code to ensure anonymity throughout transcriptions and direct quotes such as P1, P2, P3... etc. The codes will be used when quoting and referencing participants and participant codes will be stored separately from the anonymised interview transcripts.

How will my data be stored?

Data collection will be encrypted with myself and two project supervisors having access to this. I will use a secure platform to transcribe audio recordings. I will comply with all UWS Data Protection regulations, Research Data Management and NHS Code of Confidentiality. Storage of data will be held on UWS secure systems, and this will be password protected in line with UWS Protocol for the Use of Cloud Storage. When transcribing the data, I will be in a secure environment at UWS campus with no interruptions and using headphones when listening to audio recordings.

After the project has been completed?

All data recorded in all formats will be uploaded to the UWS research repository system in line with the UWS Research Data Management Procedure.

Who can I contact if I have a complaint?

If you want to complain about how researchers have handled your information, you should contact the research team. If you are not happy after that, you can contact the UWS Data Protection Officer. The research team can give you details of the right Data Protection Officer.

Will the use of my data meet GDPR rules?

GDPR stands for the General Data Protection Regulation. In the UK we follow the GDPR rules and have a law called the Data Protection Act. All research using patient data must follow UK laws and rules. Universities, NHS organisations and companies may use patient data to do research to make health and care better.

When companies do research to develop new treatments, they need to be able to prove that they need to use patient data for the research, and that they need to do the research to develop new treatments. In legal terms this means that they have a 'legitimate interest' in using patient data.

Universities and the NHS are funded from taxes and they are expected to do research as part of their job. They still need to be able to prove that they need to use patient data for the research. In legal terms this means that they use patient data as part of 'a task in the public interest'.

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Consent Form

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Ethics Approval Number: 34077

Supervisors: Dr Anna Jack-Waugh and Dr Eileen Harkess-Murphy

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Statement	Yes / No	Signature and Date
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I understand I am free to contact the researcher at any time throughout the project to ask questions.	Yes / No	

I agree to the researcher taking written notes throughout conversations.	Yes / No	
I agree to take part in this research.	Yes / No	

Consent form to be completed and returned to Kelly Kelly at

Appendix 7 – Excel TI Principles framework example

Trauma-Informed Themes				
Safety	Trustworthiness	Choice	Collaboration	Empowerment
A constant fog in my head'	Trusting services - speech therapist helped with setting small goals, suggesting a memory book	New hobby after diagnosis taking up exercise glasses	We were lucky because they were testing for parkinson's so scans had already been done'	shadow of himself'
Before the diagnosis, I was made redundant. The isolation was terrible'	Family and friends are so important'	No choice in when to receive support	we got a referral to all services'	hated giving up driving'
Every day tasks like walking the dog is too much now'		Peer support would be useful'	Once your year off YOD support is up it is like you just fall off a cliff'	knowledge is key in the understanding of young-onset dementia'
I have no clue what the future will bring'		Cafe did not work for us'	we don't know what we need and when we will need it. The first year of diagnosis was probably the best so we didn't need the support then'	We are at the very start of this'
			Given too much information in a short period of time. Websites, phones numbers etc. Overwhelmed	